

This article has been published in: Medicinal Research Reviews

Link: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/med.21717>

To cite: Wu L., **Georgiev M.L.**, Cao H., Nahar L., El-Seedi H.R., Sarker S.D., Xiao J., Lu B. (2020) Therapeutic potential of phenylethanoid glycosides: a systematic review. Medicinal Research Reviews. 40(6): 2605-2649.

First Published: 10 August 2020

Therapeutic Potential of Phenylethanoid Glycosides: A Systematic Review

Lipeng Wu^{1,2,3}, Milen I. Georgiev^{4,5}, Hui Cao^{6,5}, Lutfun Nahar^{7,6}, Hesham R. El-Seedi^{8,7,9,8}, Satyajit D. Sarker^{7,6}, Jianbo Xiao^{6,5}, Baiyi Lu^{1,2,3}

¹College of Biosystems Engineering and Food Science, National-Local Joint Engineering Laboratory of Intelligent Food Technology and Equipment, Key Laboratory for Agro-Products Nutritional Evaluation of Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, Key Laboratory of Agro-Products Postharvest Handling of Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, Zhejiang Key Laboratory for Agro-Food Processing, Zhejiang International Scientific and Technological Cooperation Base of Health Food Manufacturing and Quality Control, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou 310058, China

²Fuli Institute of Food Science, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou 310058, China

³Ningbo Research Institute, Zhejiang University, Ningbo 315100, China

⁴Laboratory of [Applied Biotechnologies](#)[Metabolomics](#), [The Stephan Angeloff](#) Institute of Microbiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

⁵[Center of Plant Systems Biology and Biotechnology, Plovdiv, Bulgaria](#)

^{6,5}[Institute of Chinese Medical Sciences, SKL of Quality Research in Chinese Medicine, University of Macau, Avenida da Universidade, Taipa, Macau.](#)

^{7,6}[Centre for Natural Products Discovery \(CNPD\), School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences, Liverpool John Moores University, James Parsons Building, Byrom Street, Liverpool L3 3AF, UK.](#)

^{8,7}Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Uppsala University, Biomedical Centre, Box 574, SE-75 123, Uppsala, Sweden

^{9,8}[International Research Center for Food Nutrition and Safety, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang 212013, China](#)

Correspondence

Jianbo Xiao, Institute of Chinese Medical Sciences, SKL of Quality Research in Chinese Medicine, University of Macau, Avenida da Universidade, Taipa, Macau. Email: jianboxiao@yahoo.com

Baiyi Lu, College of Biosystems Engineering and Food Science, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou 310058, China. Email: bylu@zju.edu.cn

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the National Major R & D Program of China (No. 2017YFD0400200), the Zhejiang Provincial Major R & D Program (No. 2019C02070), the Zhejiang Provincial Basic Public Welfare Research (No. LGN20C200010) and the Special Project of Agricultural Product Quality Safety Risk Assessment (No. GJFP2019043), Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, China. [MIG acknowledges funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, project PlantaSYST \(SGA No 739582 under FPA No. 664620\), and the BG05M2OP001-1.003-001-C01 project, financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the "Science and Education for Smart Growth" Operational Programme.](#)

Formatted: Line spacing: Double

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Abstract

Phenylethanoid glycosides (PhGs) are generally water-soluble phenolic compounds that occur in many medicinal plants. Until June 2020, more than 572 PhGs have been isolated and identified. PhGs possess antioxidant, neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, antidiabetic, anticancer, and anti-obesity properties. Despite ~~of~~ these promising benefits, PhGs have failed to fulfill ~~its~~ their therapeutic applications due to their poor bioavailability. The attempts to understand their metabolic pathways to improve their bioavailability are investigated. In this review article, we will first summarize the number of PhGs compounds which is not accurate in the literature. The latest information on the biological activities, structure-activity relationships, mechanisms and especially the clinical applications of PhGs will be reviewed. The bioavailability of PhGs will be summarized and factors leading to the low bioavailability will be analyzed. Recent advances in methods such as bioenhancers and nanotechnology to improve the bioavailability of PhGs are also summarized. The existing scientific gaps of PhGs in knowledge are also discussed, highlighting research directions in the future.

Commented [DLN1]: It is advisable to arrange in alphabetical order

Keywords: Phenylethanoid glycosides; Bioavailability; Verbascoside; Salidroside; Echinacoside

1. Introduction

Phenylethanoid glycosides (PhGs) are generally water-soluble phenolic compounds that occur in many medicinal plants. PhGs have been isolated from the roots, stems, bark, leaves, flowers, fruits and seeds of medicinal plants, as well as from suspension cell cultures, callus tissues and hairy roots cultures. They are also found in various plant-based foods such as edible flowers and tea. However, their accumulations in each [plant](#) organ may vary considerably¹⁻³. The main PhGs are reported from the families [Acanthaceae](#), [Berberidaceae](#), [Asteraceae](#), [Gesneriaceae](#), [Lamiaceae](#), [Loganiaceae](#), [Magnoliaceae](#), [Oleaceae](#), [Orobanchaceae](#), [Plantaginaceae](#), [Portulacaceae](#), [Rosaceae](#), [Scrophulariaceae](#), and [Verbenaceae](#)⁴. For example, a total of 69, 51, 21 and 16 PhGs have been isolated from *Cistanche herba*⁵, *Forsythiae fructus*⁶, *Magnoliae officinalis*⁷ and *Houttuynia cordata*⁸, respectively. Verbascoside (also known as acteoside), one of the representative PhGs, is widely distributed in the family [Lamiaceae](#), [Plantaginaceae](#), [Scrophulariaceae](#), and [Orobanchaceae](#)⁹. In 1994, Jiménez and Riguera summarized the structures and biological activities of 155 PhGs reported before 1992². In 2008, Fu et al. provided an overview in the advances on 190 new PhGs isolated from 1997 to 2007¹⁰. The detailed information of 116 new PhGs identified during 2009-2016 was given in 2016³. In the present review, we summarized the 111 PhGs¹¹⁻⁵⁶ that have not been reviewed previously (1993-1997, 2007-2009 and 2016-present) in Table 1 and Table 2. The latest new PhGs (Ginkgoside C and D) was published on 16 June 2020. Up to 572 PhGs were identified from nature until June 2020. These 572 PhGs are distributed in 21 orders and 35 families of [the plant kingdom](#) (Figure 1). It should be noted that some PhGs identified were not published in English. Thus, the actual number identified must be over 572.

In general, the basic structure of PhGs consists of a hydroxyphenylethyl unit as an aglycone which is attached to a sugar moiety mostly a β -D-glucopyranose through a glycosidic bond at the C-1 site. In most cases, the glucose moiety is esterified with a hydroxycinnamic acid derivative such as caffeic acid, coumaric acid, cinnamic acid, and ferulic acid. Rhamnose, xylose, arabinose, allose, galactose, and apiose, among others, may also be attached to the glucose residue (Figure 2, Table 1 and 2). The diversity of sugar and hydroxyphenylethyl moieties make the plentiful variation of PhGs. Generally, the number of sugars ranges from one to three. However, four-sugar and five-sugar residues are also found occasionally. According to the number of the sugars bonded to hydroxyphenylethyl moieties, PhGs can be classified into monosaccharidic PhGs, disaccharidic PhGs, trisaccharidic PhGs, tetrasaccharidic PhGs, and pentasaccharidic PhGs⁴. To date, there are 10 tetrasaccharidic PhGs reported, namely, magnolosides C⁵⁷, ballotetroside⁵⁸, trichosanthiside B⁵⁹, marruboside⁶⁰, velutinoides I⁶¹, velutinoides II⁶¹, lunariifolioside⁶²,

Commented [DLN2]: Organise in alphabetical order

raduloside⁶³, barlerinoside⁶⁴, and poliumoside B⁶⁵. Only one pentasaccharidic PhGs named yulanoside A from *M. salicifolia* was reported in 2015⁶⁶. The representative chemical structures of monosaccharidic PhGs, disaccharidic PhGs, trisaccharidic PhGs, tetrasaccharidic PhGs, and pentasaccharidic PhGs are shown in Figure 2.

Most purified PhGs are white, buff or yellow amorphous powders with high polarity. They are soluble in polar solvents but insoluble in non-polar organic solvents⁶⁷. As the characteristics of the strong ultraviolet (UV) absorption in PhGs, it is easy to monitor these compounds by UV spectrophotometer. The specific UV spectra of each PhGs can also serve as an index to deduce the structure. For example, the UV absorption peaks of verbascoside and isoverbascoside are 232, 246, 289, 332 nm, and 232, 246, 286, 328 nm, respectively⁶⁸. And that of echinacoside are 236, 288, 330 nm⁶⁹.

PhGs and the extracts rich in PhGs exhibited various benefits, such as antioxidant activity, neuroprotective effect, anti-inflammatory activity, antibacterial activity, antiviral activity, anti-diabetic activity, anti-cancer activity, and anti-obesity activity^{3,9}. Figure 3 shows the number of papers and times cited of papers indexed in the Web of Science related to “PhGs”, illustrating a significant increase in publication in this area. Although over 572 PhGs have been isolated and identified, only a few of them are extensively studied. For example, the number of papers on salidroside, verbascoside, echinacoside, forsythoside and isoverbascoside are 1746, 1258, 538, 370 and 230, respectively. And the numbers of citations of the papers about verbascoside, salidroside, echinacoside, forsythoside and isoverbascoside are 19356, 14352, 6468, 3234 and 4098, respectively. Other PhGs have fewer than 100 papers published. The number of papers published and number of citation of the papers of specific PhGs are also shown in Figure 3.

Despite of the many promising biological activities, PhGs have failed to fulfill the therapeutic applications due to poor oral-bioavailability³. The bioavailability of verbascoside was found to be 0.12% in rats after verbascoside was given at the dosages of 100 mg/kg oral administration (p.o.) and 3 mg/kg intravenous injection (i.v.)⁷⁰, but the bioavailability of verbascoside in dogs was around 4% after verbascoside was given at 40 mg/kg intragastric administration (i.g.) and 5 mg/kg i.v.⁷¹. The bioavailability of echinacoside, and angoroside C in rats at the dose of 100 mg/kg i.g. and 5 mg/kg i.v., was reported to be 0.83%⁷² and 2.1%⁷³, respectively. The bioavailability of forsythiaside (100 mg/kg p.o. and 5 mg/kg i.v.) and poliumoside (200 mg/kg p.o. and 10 mg/kg i.v.) in rats was 0.5%⁷⁴ and 0.69%⁷⁵, respectively. Feng et al. compared the pharmacokinetic and bioavailability characteristics of savaside A, verbascoside, and isoverbascoside in rats after the compounds were given at the dosages of 1000 mg/kg p.o. and 5 mg/kg i.v.. The bioavailability order of the three PhGs appears to be verbascoside > isoverbascoside > savaside A⁷⁶. Zhang et al.

Commented [DLN3]: Do we really need this statement, as all highly polar compounds behave this way.

Commented [DLN4]: List these in alphabetical order

investigated the pharmacokinetic of four PhGs (verbascoside, isoverbascoside, martynoside, and crenatoside) after orally administrated 10.0 g crude *Acanthus ilicifolius* herb /kg to rats. Although the four PhGs share similar molecular structures, they displayed different elimination half-lives ($T_{1/2}$), and different areas under the curves (AUC_{0-t}), ranging from 3.4 to 9.0 h, and 1826.3 to 23.6 $\mu\text{g/L}\times\text{h}$, respectively⁷⁷. Different dosages and administrative patterns might affect the bioavailability of PhGs. However, there is one exception. The bioavailability of salidroside was reported to be 51.97%⁷⁸. As for the reasons why the bioavailability of salidroside was significantly higher than other PhGs, this may be ascribed to its relatively simple structure (Figure. 2). Salidroside belongs to monosaccharidic PhGs consisting of phenylethanol and sucrose, and the relatively large polarity allowed it to be easily excreted from the urine without complicated metabolic processes. The higher absorption of salidroside may also lead to its obviously higher bioavailability than other PhGs (section 5.1). Numerous approaches such as bioenhancers, β -cyclodextrin encapsulation, liposomal PhGs, nanoparticles and phospholipid complex have been applied to improve the bioavailability of PhGs.

There have been a number of reviews on PhGs since the 90's. As early as 1994, Jiménez and Riguera reviewed the isolation, purification, as well as structure and biological activity of PhGs². Pan et al. highlighted the pharmacological activities of natural PhGs in 2003⁷⁹. Fu et al. summarized the phytochemistry and bioactivity of PhGs in 2008¹⁰. Radev et al. published a mini review on pharmacological effects of PhGs in 2010⁸⁰. Xue and Yang summarized advances in the phytochemistry, pharmacology and pharmacokinetics of PhGs in 2016³. Alpieva et al. reviewed the biosynthesis and pharmacological significance of verbascoside, the most popular phenylethanoid glycoside in 2014⁹. Liu et al. generalized the distribution, extraction methods, poor pharmacokinetics and therapeutic uses of echinacoside in 2018⁸¹. Tao et al. gave a detailed summary of chemical, pharmacological, toxicological, and clinical studies of various *Rhodiola* species with salidroside as the characteristic chemical constituents in 2019⁸². However, there are no comprehensive reviews concerning the stability, biotransformation, clinical application and bioavailability of PhGs. This review will summarize the latest information on the chemistry, pharmacology, stability, clinical application, pharmacokinetics, metabolites and biotransformation of PhGs. Recent advances in methods such as bioenhancers and nanotechnology to improve the bioavailability of PhGs will also be summarized. The existing scientific gaps of PhGs in knowledge are also discussed, highlighting research directions in the future.

2. Pharmacology of PhGs

PhGs have been reported to have various bioactivities in cell and animal models. Herein, the potential health benefits of PhGs are summarized (Figure 4), and the structure-activity relationship and mechanisms of PhGs' pharmacology are highlighted.

2.1 Antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity

Many PhGs and extracts rich in PhGs have shown powerful antioxidant activity. Two new PhGs named macrophyllside E and macrophyllside F, together with eight known PhGs (jionoside C, forsythoside B, alyssonoside, verbascoside, isoverbascoside, martinoside, isomartinoside and leucosceptoside) were isolated from *Callicarpa macrophylla*. All the ten PhGs showed high to moderate antioxidant effect with the IC₅₀ from 2.72 to 38.65 μM in the DPPH assay⁴³. Verbascoside isolated from *Plantago major* can significantly scavenge both DPPH radical (IC₅₀, 11.27 μM) and superoxide radicals (IC₅₀, 1.51 μM). Verbascoside can also inhibit lipopolysaccharide induced production of nitric oxide in RAW264.7 macrophages (IC₅₀, 75.0 μM)⁸³. Seven PhGs (plantalide A, verbascoside, plantamajoside, martynoside, himaloside B, desrhamnosyl isoverbascoside and plantainoside D) discovered from *P. asiatica* showed DPPH radical scavenging activity with the IC₅₀ values ranging from 22.9–88.5 μM. While other 22 compounds from *P. asiatica* showed weak antioxidant activity⁸⁵. In addition, ~~Verbascoside~~-verbascoside and salidroside were demonstrated to be two major PhGs contributing to the great antioxidant capacities of *Osmanthus fragrans* flowers⁸⁵. All nine PhGs (magnolosides Ia, Ib, Ic, IIa, IIb, IIIa, Iva, and Va and crassifolioside) from *M. officinalis* were found to possess strong free radical scavenging potential with the IC₅₀ ranging from 11.79 to 20.99 μM, and magnoloside Ia (IC₅₀, 11.79 μM) was the strongest one⁸⁶. The DPPH radical scavenging capacity of crassifolioside (IC₅₀, 21.38 μM), magnoloside IIa (22.94 μM), and magnoloside IIb (24.62 μM) was weaker than that of magnoloside Ia (11.79 μM), magnoloside Ic (12.99 μM), magnoloside Ib (16.23 μM), and magnoloside Va (20.99 μM). As we can see from the structures of these compounds, crassifolioside, magnoloside IIa and magnoloside IIb contained three sugars while magnoloside Ia, magnoloside Ic, magnoloside Ib, and magnoloside Va contained two sugars. More sugars mean larger steric hindrance in compounds and prevent them from easily approaching the free radicals, finally causing the weaker DPPH radical scavenging capacity. In addition, compared with the other seven PhGs, magnoloside IIIa (32.18 μM) and magnoloside IV (35.17 μM) with two adjacent phenolic groups only in one side exhibited poor activity⁸⁶. Furthermore, benzene ring plane conjugation in PhGs can be increased by the α, β-conjugated unsaturated ester structures and allow electron delocalization to inhibit free radicals⁸⁶.

2.2 Neuroprotective effect

Verbascoside, isoverbascoside, salidroside, and echinacoside exhibited antioxidant and neuroprotective activities in hydrogen peroxide induced apoptosis in PC12 cells via the nuclear factor erythroid 2-related pathway⁸⁷. Caleolarioside B, paraboside B, and paraboside II isolated from *Paraboea martinii* effectively protected PC12 cells from H₂O₂-induced damage by upregulating HO-1⁸⁸. It is believed that β amyloid peptide (A β) is a major cause of Alzheimer's disease⁸⁹. Total PhGs extracted from *C. Herba* at concentrations of 5, 25 and 50 μ g/mL increased the viability and decreased LDH and MDA release by PC12 cells injured with A β ₁₋₄₂⁹⁰. Torenoside B and ~~Savatiside~~ savatiside A were demonstrated to improve the enzyme activity of GSH-Px and SOD, decrease the content of MDA and ROS, and downregulate intracellular Ca²⁺ concentrations and Calnexin expression in A β ₂₅₋₃₅ induced SH-SY5Y cells⁹¹. Verbascoside, salidroside, and PhGs from *C. Herba* have significant protective potential against oxidative stress induced by A β ^{92, 93}. The characteristic pathology in Parkinson's disease is the degeneration of dopamine neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta⁹⁴. Campneoside and tubuloside B can protect neurons from 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium induced apoptosis *in vivo*^{95, 96}. Verbascoside has potential therapeutic value against PD through attenuating the oxidative stress and activating the Nrf2/ARE signaling pathway⁹⁷. SAMP8 mice, a model for AD, were administered by PhGs extracted from *C. Herba* daily intraperitoneally at 25, 50, or 100 mg/kg/day for 30 days. PhGs were found to improve cognitive deficits in SAMP8 mice by improving synaptogenesis and synaptic plasticity⁹⁸. It has been reported that the mean lifespan of *caenorhabditis elegans* was extended by 13.64% and 15.82% after treated with 200 μ M and 300 μ M ECH, respectively. The protective effect of ECH on A β -induced toxicity in *C. elegans* was almost equal to that of ginkgolide A, a well-known agent with positive effects for AD⁹⁹.

Liu et al. synthesized eight PhGs derivatives based on caleolarioside A, and studied their neuroprotective effects in PC12 cells. The results showed that seven compounds could protect the cell damage or death from the free radical damage except the chloro-substituted analog. The structure-activity relationship indicated that the catechol moiety might not monopolize the bioactivity but probably could play an important role in neuroprotection and the glucose moiety seemed not important for the neuroprotection¹⁰⁰. The findings were consistent with the recent structure-activity of caffeic acid phenethyl ester analogs^{101, 102}.

2.3 Hepatoprotective effect

Verbascoside, isoverbascoside, echinacoside, tubuloside B, cistanoside A and 2-acetyllacteosid ~~possess~~ offer

~~positively~~ hepatoprotective effects via multiple mechanisms including strengthening antioxidant defense system, free radicals scavenging, and blocking cytochrome P450 biotransformation¹⁰³. Leucoseptoside A, crenatoside, martynoside, and 3-*O*-methylcrenatoside extracted from *Incarvillea compacta* alleviated CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity by enhancing the activity of superoxide dismutase, decreasing the intracellular ROS and malondialdehyde content as well as activating NF-κB pathway¹⁰⁴. ~~14~~ Fourteen PhGs isolated from *Forsythia suspensa* were evaluated for their hepatoprotective effects on HepG2 cells damage induced by APAP. It was found that forsythoside N, forsythoside O, forsythenside A and forsythenside B exerted significant hepatoprotective activities²⁸ with the cell survival rates from 52.48% to 67.15%, 67.61%, and 64.88% at the concentration of 10 μM, respectively. Cistanoside A (125, 250, and 500 mg/kg/day) could alleviate ethanol-induced hepatotoxicity in mice by improving the activities of the activities of energy metabolism enzymes (Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺-ATPase, ATPase, and Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase), mitochondrial antioxidant enzymes (SOD, GST and CAT), and antioxidant defense system¹⁰⁵. Besides, cistanoside A (100, 75, 50, and 25 μg/mL) suppressed the apoptosis of hepatocytes by increasing the expression of Bcl-2 and suppressing c-fos¹⁰⁵. Echinacoside (60 mg/kg, i.p.) could significantly protect LPS and D-galactosamine induced acute liver injury in mice due to its anti-apoptotic and anti-inflammatory activities¹⁰⁶. PhGs from *C. deserticola* was assessed for their hepatoprotective activity *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Concentrations of 0.33, 1.00, 3.00 mg/mL PhGs ~~can~~ could improve the HepG2 cells viability to almost 10%, 22% and 35%, respectively. After orally administered with PhGs at 200, 600 or 1800 mg/kg for 31 consecutive days, ICR mice with liver injury induced by alcohol showed improved hepatic indicators (superoxide dismutase, glutathione S-transferase, glutathione, glutathione peroxidase, malondialdehyde and triglyceride) levels¹⁰⁷.

Structure–activity relationship indicated that the catechol moiety on PhGs was important for the hepatoprotective activity¹⁰⁸. Verbascoside (IC₅₀, 4.6 μM), 2'-acetylverbascoside (4.8 μM), isoverbascoside (5.3 μM), tubuloside A (8.6 μM) and echinacoside (10.2 μM) inhibited D-GalN-induced death of hepatocytes¹⁰⁹. Verbascoside (IC₅₀, 4.6 μM) showed significantly stronger activity than kankanose (>100 μM), and echinacoside (10.2 μM) showed significantly stronger activity than cistanoside F (>100 μM), which indicated that aglycone was an important group for the activity¹⁰⁹. As the activity of isoverbascoside (5.3 μM) was higher than kankanoside G (14.8 μM), it can be concluded that aglycone with the 4-hydroxy group showed weaker activity than that having 3,4-dihydroxy group¹⁰⁹. The 8-*O*-β-D-glucopyranosyl part with 6'-*O*-caffeoyl group (Tubuloside B, 14.6 μM) showed weaker activity than that with 4'-*O*-caffeoyl group (2'-acetylverbascoside, 4.8 μM)¹⁰⁹. The introduction of 6-*O*-β-D-glucopyranosyl (echinacoside < verbascoside) and 2'-*O*-acetyl moiety (2'-acetylverbascoside < verbascoside) could reduce the protective

Formatted: Font: Italic

effect¹⁰⁹.

2.4 Anti-cancer activity

In a recent study, echinacoside was reported to possess antiproliferative activities (20 µg/mL, 9.57 %; 50 µg/mL, 26.67%; 100 µg/mL, 37.20%) on HepG2 cells by inactivating AKT pathway and decreasing TREM2 expression¹¹⁰. Verbascoside, echinacoside, cistanbuloside A, cistanoside A, and 2'-acetylverbascoside inhibited the proliferation of mouse skin melanoma cancer cell line KML with the inhibition rate ranging from 33% to 93%¹¹¹. Pretreatment with 5, 10, 20, 40 and 50 µM salidroside for 48 h can inhibit the proliferation of human breast cancer MCF-7 cells to almost 70%, 60%, 55%, 45% and 30%, respectively. The mechanism maybe related with increasing caspase activity, down-regulating the Bcl-2 expression, and up-regulating the Bax expression. Moreover, salidroside treatment inhibited tumor growth in a xenograft tumor model. Compared with control group, after treated with salidroside (50 mg/kg body weight) on alternate days for 3 weeks, the weight and volume of tumor was decreased by 0.7 g and 300 mm³, respectively¹¹². Salidroside was reported to possess anti-tumor activity against Wilms' tumor¹¹³, breast cancer¹¹⁴, ovarian cancer¹¹⁵, gastric cancer¹¹⁶, skin cancer¹¹⁷, renal cell carcinoma¹¹⁸ and colorectal cancer¹¹⁹. Li et al. investigated the effects of PhGs extract from *C. tubulosa* (CTPG) on the inhibition of melanoma cell (B16-F10) growth. *In vitro*, 100 µg/mL of CTPG for 48 h or 200 µg/mL of CTPG for 72 h treatment inhibited the growth rates of B16-F10 cell to higher than 60% and 90%, respectively. CTPG can up-regulate the expressions of BAX, down-regulate the expressions of BCL-2, increase the generation of ROS, and reduce the mitochondrial membrane potential *in vitro*. Furthermore, subcutaneously administering 400 mg/kg CTPG in mice every 2 days for up to 15 days lasted the survival of mice from 8.3% to 41.7%¹²⁰. Verbascoside from *Pedicularis striata* ~~can~~ could inhibit cancer cell growth and cell cycle in G2/M phase, induce apoptosis and inhibition of telomerase activity and reduced telomere length¹²¹. It should be noted that not all PhGs exhibit anticancer properties. For example, Kirmizibekmez et al. tested the cytotoxic activity of four PhGs (plantainoside D, calceolarioside D, neocalceolarioside D and lugrandoside) against a series cancer cell lines, namely SH-SY5Y, T98G, A375, HT29, MCF-7, PC3. All the four compounds showed no toxicity against the six cancer cell lines at the concentration of 1–50 µM¹²². A number of structure-activity relationships proved that the caffeic acid moiety and catechol group are essential for the cytotoxicity of PhGs. The number of acetyl moieties and their position in the aliphatic rings also play an important role in the anti-proliferative activities of PhGs¹²³⁻¹²⁵. The antiproliferative activity of verbascoside was almost twice as that of echinacoside and calceolarioside. The similar cytotoxic activity

of calceorioside A and verbascoside suggest that rhamnose substitution does not influence the cytotoxic activity of PhGs¹²⁶. Verbascoside inhibited about 23%–30% of the proliferation activity of the cancer cells, which is almost twice as many as echinacoside (10%–18%), calceolarioside A (13%–18%), and calceolarioside B (5%–15%). The higher antiproliferative activity may be related to the α -Rha-(1→3)-Glc disaccharide unit and the 4-caffeoyl function in verbascoside¹²⁷. The structure-cytotoxicity relationships among 14 PhGs compounds indicated that the fewer sugar units they have, the stronger activities they may have. Furthermore, the position of phenolic acid does not affect the activity. Besides, methylation of the phenolic hydroxyl groups has an adverse impact on the activity¹²⁸.

2.5 Anti-inflammatory activity

The anti-inflammatory activity of PhGs is often connected to suppression of MAPK, NF- κ B, and JAK-STATs pathways and activation of Nrf2 pathway¹²⁹. Wu et al. confirmed that PhGs (verbascoside, parvifloroside A, syringalide A, 3'- α -L-rhamnopyranoside, forsythoside B, poliumoside and alyssonoside) from *C. kwangtungensis* provided protection against LPS-induced inflammatory response in RAW 264.7 macrophages by activating Keap1/Nrf2/HO-1 signaling pathway¹³⁰. Echinacoside attenuated LPS-induced inflammation in rat intestine epithelial cells by suppressing the mTOR/STAT3 pathway¹³¹. Verbascoside can inhibit the release of β -hexosaminidase, arachidonic acid and histamine in RBL-2H3 cells through inhibiting MAPK and JNK pathways and Ca²⁺ independent phospholipase¹³²⁻¹³⁴. Verbascoside (30, or 60 mg/kg) was shown to decrease inflammatory response against LPS-induced acute lung injury in mice by inhibiting NF- κ B signaling pathway¹³⁵. Gao et al. investigated the anti-inflammatory effects of verbascoside, isoverbascoside, torenoside B and savaside A and found that isoverbascoside (80 μ M), possessed the strongest activity on inhibiting the expression of iNOS and COX-2¹³⁶. Isoverbascoside exerts anti-inflammatory via modifying NF- κ B and MAPK pathways¹³⁶. Forsythiaside A was reported to have protective potential on LPS-induced inflammation in BV2 microglia cells and primary microglia cells via increasing Nrf2 and HO-1 levels and suppressing NF- κ B pathway¹³⁷. Forsythiaside A could attenuate inflammation in acute liver injury animals by activating Nrf2 and inhibiting NF- κ B pathway¹³⁸. PhGs from *Phlomis younghusbandii* exerted anti-inflammatory properties on acute hypobaric hypoxia-stimulated HACE in rats by rehabilitating the oxidative stress levels and inhibiting the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines regulated by the NF- κ B signaling pathways¹³⁹.

The anti-inflammatory activity of seven PhGs on inhibiting NO production showed that leucosceptoside A (IC₅₀, 9.0 μ M), lipedoside A-I (11.6 μ M), verbascoside (12.8 μ M), isoverbascoside (13.7 μ M), and

campneoside II (22.1 μM) possessed stronger activity than martynoside ($>100.0 \mu\text{M}$) and angoroside C ($>100.0 \mu\text{M}$). This indicated that the two adjacent hydroxide groups in PhGs may be related to their anti-inflammatory activity¹⁴⁰. Yang et al. demonstrated that PhGs with two sugar groups possessed weaker activities than others¹⁴¹.

2.6 Antiviral, antibacterial and antiprotozoal activity

Two new PhGs, Lippiarubelloside A and lippiarubelloside B, together with four known PhGs, verbascoside, isoverbascoside, forsythoside A, and poliumoside, isolated from *Lippia rubella* could strongly inhibit the growth of *Cryptococcus neoformans* at the concentrations of 15-125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ³². Total PhGs extract from *Monochasma savatieri* showed significant anti-bacterial effects at a concentration from 0.0625 to 16 mg/mL ¹⁴². Verbascoside and forsythoside B showed high antibacterial activities against five strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* from 64 g/L to 256 g/L , which were comparable to that of norfloxacin¹⁴³. When used alone at the dose of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, verbascoside had no inhibitory activity against clinical isolate of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. However, co-administration of verbascoside and gentamicin showed a synergistic effect against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. This indicated that verbascoside could be applied to overcome bacterial resistance caused by traditional medicines¹⁴⁴. Isoforsythiaside and forsythiaside are the main antibacterial constituents in *Forsythia suspensa*, which is often applied to treat the infection in upper respiratory tract. Isoforsythiaside and forsythiaside well inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*^{145, 146}. In addition, forsythoside H exhibited strong inhibitory effects against *B. vulgare*, *B. dysenteriae*, *M. pneumonia*, and *A. bacillus*¹⁴⁷. Verbascoside has anti-viral activity *in vitro* and anti-influenza activity *in vivo*. And the anti-viral mechanism of verbascoside was related to the activation of ERK and enhancement of IFN- γ production¹⁴⁸. Forsythiaside and calceolarioside B showed significant antiviral potential on respiratory syncytial virus *in vitro*¹⁴⁹. Forsythiaside inhibited the infectivity of avian infectious bronchitis virus¹⁵⁰. Taraffinisoside A, a new PhGs isolated from *Tarphochlamys affinis*, showed antihepatitis B activity with IC_{50} values of 0.50 and 0.93 mM against hepatitis B surface antigen and hepatitis B e antigen, respectively⁶⁷. Forsythoside A from *F. suspensa* decreased the viral titers of different influenza virus subtypes in cell cultures at the dose of 160 μM . Forsythoside A also increased the survival rate of the mice in an influenza virus infection model at 5 or 10 $\mu\text{g/g}$ body weight¹⁵¹. Hu et al. evaluated the anti-influenza virus effects of PhGs *in vitro* and *in vivo*. PhGs at 0.5 mg/mL could inhibit the influenza A virus H1N1 type infection of Madin Darby canine kidney cell *in vitro*. PhGs at 300 and 900 mg/kg significantly reduced the mouse lung index ($p < 0.05$), alleviated influenza-induced lethality and clinical

symptoms, and prolonged mouse survival time ($p < 0.05$). The mechanism maybe related to up-regulating IFN- γ ¹⁵².

It has been reported that verbascoside possessed antiprotozoal activity against *Trypanosoma brucei rhodesiense*, *Leishmania infantum*, *L. donovani*, and *L. amazonensis*^{153, 154}. Verbascoide showed an EC₅₀ of 19 μ M against *L. promastigotes* and is a competitive arginase inhibitor with Ki of 0.7 μ M¹⁵⁵. Among seven PhGs extracted from *Tecoma mollis*, luteoside B and luteoside A showed the strongest antileishmanial activity with the IC₅₀ values of 6.7 and 15.1 μ g/mL, respectively¹⁵⁶.

Little information is available about the structure-activity relationship of PhGs in its antiviral and antibacterial activities. Kyriakopoulou et al. discovered that samioside is more active than verbascoside against four strains of bacteria, indicating that an additional sugar moiety (apiose) at C-4 of rhamnose could contribute to the antibacterial activity¹⁵⁷. Although phlinoside C and forsythoside B have a similar structure, phlinoside C hardly inhibit multi-drug-resistant strains of *S. aureus*. This indicated that introducing the third glycoside (rhamnose) to forsythoside B might cause its inactivity¹⁴³.

2.7 Antidiabetic activity

A new PhGs named flavaioside from *Scrophularia flava* showed α -glucosidase inhibitory activities with IC₅₀ value of 6.50 μ g/mL. In addition, flavaioside possessed a significant inhibitory activity on the α -glucosidase enzyme, and the inhibitory activity (91.85%) was comparable with the known anti-type 2 diabetic drug, acarbose (92.87%)¹⁵⁸. The *in vitro* experiments showed that verbascoside, echinacoside, isoverbascoide, 2'-acetylverbascoside, tubulosides A, tubulosides B, syringalide A' 3-O-rhamnose, campneoside I, and kankanoside J₁ from *C. tubulosa* could offer strong inhibition against lens aldose reductase with their IC₅₀ of 3.1, 1.2, 4.6, 0.071, 8.8, 4.0, 11.1, 0.53, and 9.3 μ M, respectively. Especially, 2'-acetylverbascoside showed the similar activity with epalrestat, a clinical aldose reductase inhibitor¹⁵⁹. Verbascoide and echinacoside were demonstrated to improve glucose tolerance and decrease glucose level in mice at doses of 250-500 mg/kg¹⁵⁹. Verbascoide and echinacoside could suppress the increased postprandial blood glucose level by inhibiting glucose transporter 1-mediated glucose uptake¹⁶⁰. Isocampneoside II isolated from *P. coreana* could significantly inhibit recombinant human aldose reductase with the IC₅₀ of 9.72 μ M. Furthermore, verbascoside, isoverbascoide, isocampneoside II and cistanoside F effectively inhibited sorbitol accumulation in a rat lens incubated with a high concentration of glucose by almost 70.6, 47.9, 71.3, and 31.7% at 50 μ M, respectively¹⁶¹. Compared with control group, three weeks oral administration of verbascoside (10, 20, and 40 mg/kg) caused a significant reduction of blood glucose

to 111.30, 74.88, and 75.15 mg/dL, respectively, in diabetic rats. Regarding serum insulin levels, oral treatment with verbascoside (10, 20, and 40 mg/kg) elevated the serum insulin level to be 3.23, 5.38, and 6.80 μ IU/mL, respectively, in diabetic rats¹⁶².

2.8 Other activities

Wu et al. investigated the anti-obesity properties of PhGs from *Ligustrum purpurascens*. The results showed that PhGs inhibited α -chymotrypsin, trypsin and pepsin with the IC₅₀ values of 0.42, 0.38, and 0.68 mg/mL, respectively. Verbascoside exerted the anti-obesity effects by inhibiting pancreatic lipase. Verbascoside bounded to lipase at $K_a = 1.88 \times 10^4 / 1 \text{ mol}^{163}$. The anti-obesity effect of PhGs from *L. purpurascens* against fatty diet-fed mice was associated with the up-regulating of mRNA and protein levels of adipose leptin¹⁶⁴. Echinacoside (0.01-10 nmol/L) was reported to boost bone regeneration in MC3T3-E1 cells by enhancing receptor activator of NF- κ B ligand (RANKL)¹⁶⁵. Similarly, 12 weeks' daily i.g. administration of echinacoside (30, 90, and 270 mg/kg/day) to ovariectomized (OVX) rats significantly increased osteoprotegerin (OPG) level and decreased RANKL level¹⁶⁶. Compared to OVX group, 270 mg/kg/day echinacoside treatment caused the highest levels of OPG and OPG/RANKL ratios (150.14% and 197.64%)¹⁶⁶. After 12 weeks' daily orally administration of echinacoside (30, 90, 270 mg/kg/day) in OVX rats, the urine concentration of calcium, inorganic phosphorus, and hydroxyproline was increased by 92.23%, 66.67% and 36.41%, respectively, in 270 mg/kg/day group¹⁶⁷. Cistanoside A (p.o., 20, 40 and 80 mg/kg/day for 12 weeks) was found to promote bone formation and prevent bone resorption in OVX rats by downregulating TRAF6, coordinating the inhibition of NF- κ B pathway and stimulating PI3K/Akt pathway¹⁶⁸.

3. Clinical applications of PhGs

Although PhGs exhibit many bioactivities in cell or animal models, the poor bioavailability of PhGs restricts their clinical applications. Various PhGs-based products including Traditional Chinese Medicines (oral liquid, capsules and tablets), dietary supplements and tea are summarized in Figure 5.

In a randomized, single-center and double-blind clinical trial (phase II) conducted in 100 patients having cardiovascular risk factors, orally administration of verbascoside tablet (50 mg/tablet, twice daily) for 2 weeks can significantly decrease platelet aggregation (PA) from 51% to 39%¹⁶⁹. According to the ongoing and unpublished clinical trials about PhGs on the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (<http://apps.who.int/trialsearch>), a comparative evaluation of verbascoside and silymarin as

hepatoprotective agents in acute hepatitis patients had been performed (Main ID: CTRI/2008/091/000247), but the results were not provided in the platform. Qiu et al. assessed the efficacy of verbascosides from *Rehmannia glutinosa* combined with irbesartan in treating chronic primary glomerulonephritis in 479 patients. The patients were randomly divided into treatment group (*Rehmannia-R. glutinosa* verbascoside, 200 mg/capsule, two capsules one time, twice daily; and irbesartan, 150 mg/tablet, one capsules one time, once daily) and the control group (irbesartan, 150 mg/tablet, one capsule one time, once daily). After 8 weeks treatment, the mean reduction of proteinuria in 24h in treatment group (36.42%) was significantly higher than that in control group (27.97%), indicating the combination of *R. glutinosa* verbascosides and irbesartan can reduce proteinuria more effectively than irbesartan alone¹⁷⁰. From the website of Clinicaltrials.gov., a phase II clinical study (Identifier: NCT02662283) had been conducted to test the therapy effect of Reh-verbascoside (general verbascoside from rehmanniae leaves) in patients with immune globulin a nephropathy. But it is a pity that the results of this clinical trial are not available from the website. Salidroside powder (600 mg/day) was shown to prevent the symptom of early left ventricular regional systolic dysfunction caused by epirubicin in 60 patients with breast cancer¹⁷¹.

In China, *C. tubulosa* glycosides (CTG, Memoregain®) have been approved as a treatment for vascular dementia and produced by Sinphar Tianli Pharmaceutical Company (Hangzhou, China) (Figure 5). This is the first Chinese government approved drug containing PhGs. An open-label, no placebo-controlled clinical trial was conducted to study the effect of CTG capsules for treating AD. A total of 18 patients with AD were administered by 300 mg CTG capsules, 3 times per day for 48 weeks. The Mini-Mental State Examination score, Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale–cognitive subscale score, Activities of Daily Living score, Blessed Behavioral Scale, and Clinical Global Impression scales all showed no significant difference from baseline, indicating that AD patients did not show significant aggravation of cognitive function after 48 weeks¹⁷². Observations from 131 patients with vascular dementia showed that CTG (0.3 g/capsule, 6 capsules per day, 3 months) was more effective than positive control (hydergine, 1 mg/ tablet, 6 tablets per day, 3 months) against vascular dementia¹⁷³. Peng et al. and Yuan et al. also reported that CTG (0.3 g/capsule, 6 capsules per day, 48 weeks) can improve cognitive function in the early dementia and mild dementia patients^{174, 175}. From the website of <http://apps.who.int/trialsearch>, a clinical trial about CTG for treatment of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis has been carried out (Main ID: ChiCTR10R-15006524). Hopefully, the results of this clinical trial will be published soon. Echinacoside is one of the active ingredients in *C. Herba* and the main active component of Memoregain®. In addition, two new agents named Echinacoside and Naoqing Zhiming tablet derived from echinacoside have been approved for

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

Commented [DLN5]: State full name. Citrus?

clinical trials by the Chinese government in 2107. It should be noted that the clinical trials of Echinacoside and Naoqing Zhiming tablet were applied by Huayi Shennong Pharmaceutical Company (Beijing, China) set up by Prof. Tu Pengfei from School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Peking University. Prof. Tu has made great contribution to the development of *Cistanche deserticola* industry, and Memoregain(®) was also developed based on the researches of Prof. Tu. It has been demonstrated that *cistanches herba* capsule (0.3 g/capsule, 3 capsules per day, 48 weeks) could increase cognitive abilities in AD patient's and slow down their hippocampus atrophy process. It also decreased the expressions of TNF- α , T-tau, and IL-1 β in cerebrospinal fluid of AD patients as the similar effect as Donepezil tablet (5mg/tablet, 1 tablet per day, 48 weeks)¹⁷⁶.

Herbs used together, rather than a single herb or a single compound, are the commonly used forms in traditional Chinese medicines (TCM), and often have significant clinical effects. PhGs are the active and characteristic compounds of *F. forsythiae*¹⁷⁷. And *F. forsythiae* has been extensively used in TCM preparations, such as Shuang Huang Lian oral liquid, Niu Huang Shang Qing tablets and Yin Qiao Jie Du tablets, etc., which have long been used to treat respiratory tract infection¹⁷⁸ (Figure 5). In the 2015 edition of Chinese Pharmacopoeia, over one hundred TCM preparations containing *F. Forsythiae* are listed (Pharmacopoeia Commission of PRC, 2015). Another example is that Bu Shen Huo Xue Granule with *C. Herba* as a main active component, can significantly improve the clinical symptom of patients with PD¹⁷⁹.

4. Stability of PhGs

As we can see from the chemical structure of PhGs, there are several phenolic hydroxyl groups, ester bonds and glycosidic bonds, which makes them be easily oxidized and degraded. In addition, the intra-molecular acyl migration, and *cis-/trans* configurational conformation of acyl and glycosyl widely occur in this chemical cluster. These structural properties make PhGs labile compounds. PhGs are vulnerable to be degraded by various factors such as light, temperature and pH in theory.

PhGs were found to be unstable under light exposure, high temperature, and high pH conditions¹⁸⁰. The content of total PhGs (TPG) of *O. fragrans* flowers in water for 90 days was significantly decreased by 87% at 50 °C. And TPG was degraded by 84.25% after 7 days at 80 °C. Increasing of pH (from 5.0 to 9.0) accelerated the degradation of PhGs. At the same temperature (20 °C), the degradation rate of TPG in light was significantly higher than dark, indicating PhGs were unstable in light. The degradation patterns of salidroside and verbascoside were the same of TPG¹⁸⁰. Verbascoside was more stable in a weak acid medium, low temperature and dark conditions. Under the condition of pH 7, verbascoside was completely

degraded after two weeks (room temperature) and three weeks (40 °C). While the degradation rate of verbascoside was 27% over 60 days, in the dark and room temperature at the pH of 5¹⁸¹. Oyourou et al. assessed the stability of verbascoside in crude plant extract during storage. After 2 and 4 h exposure to sunlight, only 43.2% and 18.6% of the verbascoside were remained in the extract¹⁸².

In order to imitate the storage condition of verbascoside at room temperature for two years, verbascoside was put in an oven at 56 °C for 2 weeks. Verbascoiside in crude plant extract was found to significantly decompose, with only 13.7% left after 2 weeks' exposure. It indicated that verbascoside is unstable after stored for a long period¹⁸². Verbascoiside in bitter tea was isomerized to isoverbascoiside when heated in the boiling water¹⁸³, while verbascoside remains intact during the process of steam pasteurization at 99 °C for 150 s¹⁸⁴. This phenomenon was inconsistent with the findings that 98.2% and 5.4% of verbascoside was left following steam distillation and hydrodistillation, respectively¹⁸². It has been reported that 62.4% and 100% of verbascoside were left at pH 7 and 3, respectively, after 24 h¹⁸⁵. The reduction level of verbascoside at pH 7 was in agreement with the results of Vertuani et al.¹⁸¹. Verbascoiside was moderately stable during digestive conditions *in vitro* with a recovery rate of 53%, while isoverbascoiside was less stable with a recovery rate of 13%¹⁸⁶. When echinacoside was stored in methanol, two primary products verbascoside and cistanoside A, could be observed by HPLC chromatogram. And *cis*-echinacoside, *cis*-verbascoside, and *cis*-cistanoside A were detected after careful analysis of the 1H-NMR spectra of echinacoside, verbascoside and cistanoside A. These findings indicated that methylation and hydrolysis are the main transformation pathways of echinacoside in methanol, and mild transformation could also occur by *cis/trans*-configuration transferring in the caffeoyl group¹⁸⁷. PhGs were reported to be stable in tincture with 80% left after 6 months, probably because of the weak acid medium in tincture¹⁸⁸.

5. Pharmacokinetics of PhGs

The main pharmacokinetic parameters of several PhGs in plasma are summarized in Table 3^(70-76, 78, 189-194).

5.1 Absorption

The absorption of salidroside, verbascoside, isoverbascoiside and echinacoside in Caco-2 cells were poor, and their transportation was mainly via passive diffusion (less than 3.0%)^{195, 196}. Verbascoiside was poorly absorbed with low apparent permeability (Papp) (4.75×10^{-7} cm/s). The peak accumulation of verbascoside and isoverbascoiside was at 30 min *in vitro*, indicating their rapid uptake. But the uptake efficiency was very low (0.1-0.2%)¹⁹⁶. The intestinal absorption of verbascoside in viable and healthy human colonic tissues demonstrated that verbascoside was absorbed rapidly, but the total accumulation efficiency was less than

0.12%. Major absorption of verbascoside happened in proximal tract of colon (5 to 15 min), and then it was descending to colon (30 to 60 min) and sigmoid rectum colon after 60 min¹⁹⁷. A bioavailability study of oral versus intravenous verbascoside dosing in rats reported that verbascoside given at the dose thirty times higher than the intravenous dose, lead to the C_{max} of 0.13 and 48.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and the $T_{1/2}$ of 92.1 and 10.7 min for oral and intravenous routes, respectively³⁰. Similarly, verbascoside was reported to be absorbed extremely fast in rats. However, the maximum serum concentration was very low (C_{max} , 312.54 ng/mL)¹⁸⁹. The uptake of verbascoside and plantamajoside was very quick with T_{max} values of 13.3 and 16.7 min, respectively. C_{max} values of verbascoside and plantamajoside in plasma were 135.5 and 172.3 ng/mL, respectively¹⁹⁸.

Echinacoside permeated poorly with the Papp of zero after 90 min *in vitro*. The uptake of echinacoside was at the same level of mannitol which is a known poor intestinal absorption compound¹⁹⁹. Echinacoside can pass the intestinal barrier through carrier-mediated transport. The Peff values of jejunum, duodenum, and ileum was at the same level (0.006 $\mu\text{g}/\text{s}$), higher than that of colon (0.002 $\mu\text{g}/\text{s}$), suggesting that intestinal absorption of echinacoside was site dependent²⁰⁰. Echinacoside was absorbed quickly after i.g. administration at 100 mg/kg in rats, exhibiting the C_{max} of 312.54 ng/mL after 0.29 h. However, the maximum serum concentration was very low with the C_{max} of 612.2 ng/mL³². In humans, echinacoside cannot be detected in plasma after echinacea tablet ingestion²⁰¹.

The permeability of forsythiaside A in the basolateral-to-apical direction was similar to that in apical-to-basolateral direction in Caco-2 cell model²⁰². A similar research indicated that the absorption of forsythiaside A was mainly involved with paracellular transport route, and P-glycoprotein, multidrug resistance related proteins and uptake transporters might participate in its uptake in the intestine²⁰³. In addition, no statistical difference of absorption was found for forsythiaside among gastric, duodenum, jejunum, ileum and colon, indicating no specific absorption site of forsythiaside²⁰⁴. When given i.g. administration of 100 mg/kg forsythiaside to rats, a maximum serum concentration of 122.2 ng/mL was observed at 20 min⁷³.

The rapid but low absorption was also found in poliumoside and angoroside C. After i.g. administration of poliumoside at 200 mg/kg in rats, the T_{max} and C_{max} were calculated to be 30 min and 561 ng/mL, respectively. Angoroside C can be absorbed extremely quickly ($T_{max}=15$ min) after oral administration and can be eliminated very rapidly ($T_{1/2}$, 1.26 h)⁷⁵.

Unlike the rapid but low absorption pattern of the PhGs summarized above, salidroside was reported to have a rapid and high absorption. After p.o. administration of 5 mg/kg salidroside in rats, salidroside showed

rapid oral absorption with a T_{max} of 30 min. The C_{max} of salidroside was approximately 6493 ng/mL, which is almost twenty times higher than that of verbascoside and echinacoside¹⁹². Salidroside has a rapid and high absorption with the C_{max} of 3716.73 ng/mL and 4300 ng/mL, after i.g. administration of 100 mg/kg and 12 mg/kg in rats, respectively^{78, 193}. The high absorption of salidroside may lead to its obviously higher bioavailability than other PhGs.

5.2 Body Distribution

The distribution of PhGs in tissues is crucial for its bioactivity, although only few studies have reported on it. Wen et al. investigated the distribution of verbascoside in rats after p.o. administration (40 mg/kg) and found that verbascoside reached maximum level in most organs at 0.17 or 0.50 h post-administration. The highest concentration of verbascoside occurred in intestine (26474.50 ng/gtissue), followed by lung (23 466.07), stomach (19918.21) and muscle (9498.13). The levels of verbascoside in intestine, lung, stomach and muscle were significantly higher than that in other tissues like spleen, kidney, liver, heart, brain, adipose, ovary and testis¹⁸⁹. After 0.17 h, verbascoside cannot be detected in ovary and testis. Verbascoiside in adipose and in kidney was undetectable after 1.5 h. The levels of verbascoside in all tissues remarkably reduced after 1.5 h, suggesting verbascoside cannot cause accumulative damage effect *in vivo*. In addition, a little amount of verbascoside was detected in brain, indicating verbascoside can pass the blood-brain barrier¹⁸⁹. The verbascoside concentration in different brain regions ranged from 0.45 to 0.68%. There was no statistical difference of verbascoside concentration in different brain regions (brain stem, cerebellum, hippocampus, striatum, cerebral cortex, and the rest of brain) after i.v. administration of 10 mg/kg verbascoside in rats⁷⁰. After i.g. administration of 200 mg/kg verbascoside and 200 mg/kg echinacoside in rats, their relative content in plasma, feces, urine and bile was calculated. Only 1.54% of echinacoside and no verbascoside was detected in plasma²⁰⁵. Sibirioside A (200 mg/kg) and angoroside C (200 mg/kg) from *S. Radix* were widely distributed in heart, lung, liver, stomach, kidney, and small intestine in rats²⁰⁶. The highest content of sibirioside A was in stomach and small intestine, followed by the kidney and liver. But no angoroside C was detected in the viscera except for stomach and small intestine. The highest level of angoroside C was found in lung 15 min after p.o. administration and angoroside C is distributed rapidly and cannot be detected from all of the organs after 6 h²⁰⁶.

Distribution study in rats after i.v. administration of 15 mg/kg salidroside showed that salidroside distributed rapidly into tissues after 15 min²⁰⁷. At all three time points (15, 40 and 120 min), the concentration of salidroside in plasma was higher than that in any tissues. Half of the unchanged salidroside

Commented [DLN6]: The standard term ADME stands for absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion/elemination.

was detected in urine over 48 h, but only 0.89 ‰ and 1.8 ‰ was detected in bile and feces, respectively²⁰⁷. Compared with i.g. administration, the distribution of salidroside in rats changed greatly under i.v. administration. After i.v. administration of salidroside (50 mg/kg) to rats, the maximum levels of salidroside were mainly in liver, kidney and heart. However, salidroside was only found in liver after i.g. administration of salidroside (100 mg/kg)²⁰⁸. After 72 h, 64% and 23.8% of the administered salidroside was excreted in the urine, after i.v. administration and i.g. administration, respectively. After 72 h, 0.3% of the administered amount was detected in feces after i.v. administration, while no salidroside was detected in faeces after i.g. administration²⁰⁸.

5.3 Metabolites *in vivo*

–Based on the metabolic pathways mentioned below, the metabolic pathways of PhGs *in vivo* are shown in Figure 6. 35 metabolites in rats orally administrated with verbascoside (100 mg/kg) were detected in rat urine. 19 metabolites belong to the parent compound and 16 metabolites belong to the degraded products of verbascoside. The metabolism processes include oxidation, glucuronidation, sulfation, and methyl conjugation, with methylation of the most easily occurred²⁰⁹. Verbascoiside was easily hydrolyzed to degraded products, which is responsible for its low oral bioavailability²⁰⁹. After p.o. administration of verbascoside, 44 metabolites were identified in rats' plasma, urine, and feces samples. This is the first time to report the isomerization of verbascoside to isoverbascoiside²¹⁰.

Eight metabolites of echinacoside, mainly methylation and glucuronidation conjugates, were found in the biliary of rats after oral dose of 200 mg/kg echinacoside²¹¹. A later study identified 13 metabolites of echinacoside in rat urine and feces samples after p.o. administration of 1500 mg/kg echinacoside²¹². In 2019, Song et al. reported that 19 metabolites were identified in blood, urine and feces samples of echinacoside (50 mg/kg, i.g.) treated rats by analyzing m/z values, retention time, and optimal collision energy. Echinacoside firstly underwent extensively hydrolysis to generate verbascoside, followed by intermediates such as caffeic acid and hydroxytyrosol. Afterwards, the two intermediates received sulfonation, glucuronidation, methylation, oxidation, reduction, and/or hydrogenation to finally generate M1–M16. In addition, acyl-migration and acetylation of verbascoside (M17) produced isoverbascoiside (M18) and acetyl-verbascoside (M19)²¹³. 3 metabolites of forsythiaside A (200 mg/kg, p.o.) were identified in rats, with 42 in urine, 22 in plasma and 15 in feces²¹⁴. In general, forsythiaside A was mainly methylated, dimethylated, sulfated, glucuronidated, diglucuronidated, and cysteine conjugated. Hydroxyl group on caffeic acid of forsythiaside A was the major target metabolic site²¹⁴. 66 metabolites of poliumoside (1000

mg/kg, p.o.) in rat feces samples were identified. The metabolic pathways of poliumoside involving in phase I were hydroxylation, hydration, hydrolysis, methoxylation, dehydrogenation and reduction; while the phase II reactions were sulfation, dimethylation and acetylation. And hydroxylation was more likely to occur in the metabolic process. Verbascoside is a key degraded product of poliumoside²¹⁵. After oral administration of poliumoside (1500 mg/kg), 34 poliumoside metabolites (30 from urine, 17 from plasma, and 4 from bile) were identified, which also demonstrated that verbascoside was a main degraded product of poliumoside and mainly existed in urine. The nine metabolic pathways of poliumoside were proposed as rearrangement, reduction, hydroxylation, hydration, dehydration, methylation, acetylation, hydrolyzation, and sulfation²¹⁶, which are partly in accordance with the result of Deng et al.²¹⁵. Metabolites of salidoside in rats plasma samples indicated that salidoside was metabolized through glucuronidation, deglycosylation, sulfation, methylation, hydroxylation, and dehydroxylation *in vivo*²¹⁷. After p.o. administration of *C. tubulosa* extract (400 mg/kg), the *in vivo* metabolites in urine and fecal were obviously different in healthy and chronic unpredictable stress model rats. The metabolic ability to generate secondary glycosides and aglycones in depressive rat intestinal microbiota was much weaker than that in normal rat intestinal microbiota. The reason may be related to structural changes of the intestinal microbiota induced by depression, which finally lead to decreased activity of related enzymes produced by intestinal microbiota²¹⁸. The metabolites of angoroside C and sibirioside A were studied after orally administrating 200 mg/kg compounds to rats²⁰⁶. 25 metabolites of angoroside C were found mainly in urine via hydrolyzation, dehydroxylation hydrogenation, gluconylation, demethylation, and sulfation. And gluconylation was the prime and representative metabolic reaction²⁰⁶. As for sibirioside A, four metabolites were found, with one in urine, two in feces, and one in stomach. The less metabolites of sibirioside A maybe due to its simple molecular structure. The main metabolic reactions of sibirioside A were hydrogenation, sulfation, hydroxylation, dimerization methylation, and glycosylation²⁰⁶.

6. Biotransformation of PhGs by microbiota *in vitro*

Intestinal bacteria are mainly involved in reduction, hydroxylation and hydrolyzation²¹⁹. The metabolites of verbascoside in human or rat intestinal bacteria confirmed this point. Verbascoside was biotransformed to 14 metabolites through a series of reactions including isomerization, hydroxylation, hydrogenation, and dihydroxylation. The main metabolites of verbascoside was caffeic acid, hydroxytyrosol and m-hydroxyphenylpropanoic acid²²⁰. Similarly, metabolites of verbascoside by intestinal bacteria *in vitro* were also identified by another two studies^{221,222}. The metabolites may lead to the low bioavailability of

verbascoside *in vivo*.

The metabolism of echinacoside in human fecal microbial *in vitro* showed that the deglycosylation, reduction, hydroxylation, dehydroxylation, and acetylation were the main pathways to generate 13 echinacoside metabolites. The metabolites mainly include verbascoside, caffeic acid, hydroxytyrosol, m-hydroxyphenylpropanoic acid, and dihydrocaffeic acid²²³. Only caffeic acid, hydroxytyrosol and dihydrocaffeic acid were found in the metabolites of forsythoside A by human intestinal bacteria *in vitro*. It was proposed that caffeic acid was produced by hydrolyzing forsythoside A, and was hydrogenated further to form 3,4-dihydroxybenzenepropionic acid²²⁴.

11-Eleven metabolites of verbascoside, seven metabolites of isoverbascoside, and 11 metabolites of 2-acetylverbascoside generated by gut microbiota were found via metabolic pathways including deglycosylation, deacetylation, dehydroxytyrosol, decaffeoyl, acetylation, reduction, and sulfate conjugation²²⁵. All the intermediates of verbascoside and isoverbascoside produced by gut microbiota were transformed to 3-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid and hydroxytyrosol after 48 h incubation, which is in consistent with the echinacoside microbial metabolisms²²³. Li et al. confirmed that PhGs were more likely to be biotransformed to their caffeic acid and aglycones derivatives via glucuronidation and deglycosylation and by human intestinal bacteria *in vitro*²²⁶. However, only 30% of echinacoside from the *C. tubulosa* extract was metabolized after incubated with gut microbiota for 48 h, while another research demonstrated that echinacoside was completely metabolized after incubation with gut microbiota for 48 h²²³. The difference in the metabolism of single compound and the *C. tubulosa* extract was probably because of the presences of oligosaccharides and polysaccharides in the plant extract.

7. Bioactivities of PhGs ~~Metabolites~~metabolites

As mentioned in section 2, PhGs exhibit extensive strong activities. However, clear pharmacological characteristics such as poor absorption, extensive and fast metabolism in the gut, liver and blood, lead to their extremely low bioavailability of PhGs. Thus, there is some controversy with regard to whether PhGs themselves are the primary compounds contributing significantly to the beneficial activities, or whether the activity of their metabolites are responsible for the biological activities.

It is worth noting that the main and common degradation products of PhGs, such as caffeic acid and hydroxytyrosol, and the derivatives of caffeic acid and hydroxytyrosol, are reported to possess potent antioxidant with many health benefits^{227, 228}. The antioxidant activity of several PhGs, caffeic acid-related metabolites, and hydroxytyrosol-related metabolites were evaluated by the DPPH assay²²⁹. The

metabolites showed stronger activity than PhGs. Their antioxidant activity decreased in the following order: ferulic acid (hydroxytyrosol-related), 3,4-dihydroxybenzenepropanoic acid (caffeic acid-related), caffeic acid, tubuloside B, verbascoside, isoverbascoside, tubuloside A, poliumoside, hydroxytyrosol and echinacoside with the IC₅₀ values of 1.312, 1.556, 1.601, 2.469, 3.166, 3.235, 3.452, 3.613, 3.952 and 4.799 µg/mL, respectively²²⁹. It has also been reported that caffeic acid and hydroxytyrosol were more active than verbascoside and isoverbascoside in antiprotein glycation activities *in vitro*²³⁰. The antimicrobial activity of forsythoside A, and its metabolites such as caffeic acid, hydroxytyrosol and 3,4-dihydroxybenzenepropanoic acid (DCA) was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method *in vitro*. Caffeic acid has no activity, and hydroxytyrosol displayed the highest antimicrobial activity, followed by forsythoside A and DCA. The MIC values of forsythoside A, hydroxytyrosol and DCA against *S. aureus* are 25, 50 and 50 µg/mL, respectively²²⁴. The antiendotoxin activities of forsythoside A, caffeic acid, hydroxytyrosol and DCA were determined by the LAL assay *in vitro*. The results showed forsythoside A and caffeic acid were invalid even at the maximal concentration (1000 µg/mL). While hydroxytyrosol and DCA were still effective when diluted four and three times, respectively²²⁴. It was found that verbascoside metabolites such as hydroxytyrosol, caffeic acid and 3-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid (3-HPP), possessed higher hepatoprotective activities than verbascoside through regulating oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, and inflammatory responses in a GalN/LPS induced acute hepatic-injury mouse model at the dosage of 0.15 mmol/kg²³¹. In addition, dihydrocaffeic acid exhibited protective activities on ischemia-induced neuronal damage and brain edema cerebral on a focal cerebral ischemia rat model²³². Besides, m-hydroxyphenylpropanoic acid displayed antioxidant effect²³⁴ and decaffeoyl verbascoside possessed anti-inflammatory activity *in vivo and in vitro*²³³. Therefore, we can make the conclusion that the metabolites of PhGs such as hydroxytyrosol, caffeic acid, 3-HPP, DCA, decaffeoyl verbascoside and m-hydroxyphenylpropanoic are the active substances *in vivo*.

Further comparative studies would be of great value, to confirm whether the administration of PhGs metabolites is more beneficial than traditional PhGs administration. Even if PhGs metabolites showed promising activities when tested alone *in vivo and in vitro*, whether the concentration of metabolites can reach the concentration that make it effective *in vivo* needs to be carefully considered. Thus, strategies to enhance the bioavailability of PhGs are still highly significant.

8. Approaches to improve the bioavailability of PhGs

Numerous approaches such as bioenhancers, β-cyclodextrin encapsulation, liposomal PhGs, nanoparticles and phospholipid complex have been applied to improve the bioavailability of PhGs (Figure 7).

8.1 Bioenhancers

Low intestinal absorption is one of the most important factors causing the low bioavailability of PhGs. Some plant essential oils such as borneol, pennyroyal and clove oil could act as absorption promoters to improve intestinal absorption of active compounds^{235, 236}. Moreover, some efflux proteins such as P-glycoprotein (P-gp) belonging to ATP-binding cassette transporters superfamily, and multidrug resistance protein (MRP) are abundant in the human intestines, and play a significant role in drug absorption, transport, and bioavailability^{237, 238}. Efflux protein inhibitors are potential to enhance the bioavailability of several important anticancer drugs (anthracyclines, taxanes, etc.) by occupying the drug binding sites as a competitive blocker, binding chemosensitizer sites as a non-competitive antagonist, altering P-gp expression or inhibiting the ATPase function and related proteins^{239, 240}.

Several bioavailability enhancers have been applied to improve the bioavailability of PhGs. The addition of 320 μM epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) significantly increased the Papp(AP \rightarrow BL) value of verbascoside (320 μM) to 5.69×10^{-7} cm/s in Caco-2 monolayers. Further pharmacokinetics study of verbascoside in rats demonstrated that after oral administration of 200 mg/kg verbascoside and 200 mg/kg EGCG, the AUC of verbascoside was increased to 1.43 fold that of pure verbascoside²⁴¹. It was shown that the Papp value of forsythoside A *in vitro* Caco-2 monolayer model was significantly increased to 208% and 206% by 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ water-soluble chitosan and 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ sodium caprate, respectively. Pharmacokinetics study of forsythoside A in rat showed that AUC_{0-480 min} (ng min/mL) of forsythoside A, forsythoside A with 100 mg/kg sodium caprate, and forsythoside A with 50 mg/kg water-soluble chitosan was 6396.5, 11041 and 12412.7, respectively²⁴². A similar research also demonstrated that the absorption of forsythoside A in SHL was increased by absorption enhancers such as water-soluble chitosan and sodium caprate²⁴². 10, 32 and 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ water-soluble chitosan increased the Papp value to 119%, 206% and 165% in Caco-2 cells²⁴². And the Papp value was increased to 128%, 175% and 208% after the addition of 10, 32 and 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of the sodium caprate²⁴². 100 mg/kg sodium caprate and 50 mg/kg water-soluble chitosan increased the AUC_{0-t} from 6396.5 ng min/mL to 11041.5 and 10597.0 ng min/mL, respectively, in rats²⁴².

The P_{app} values of forsythoside B, isoforsythoside, and forsythoside A were significantly improved to 1282%, 989.6%, and 561.0% with the addition of 0.1% chito-oligosaccharide (COS)²⁴³. The C_{max} values of isoforsythoside, and forsythoside B, forsythoside A were increased to 214%, 185.4%, and 161%, respectively. Besides, the AUC values of forsythoside A, isoforsythoside and forsythoside B were enhanced to 290%, 252% and 214%, respectively, after the addition of 25 mg/kg COS²⁴³. The C_{max} values of 0.09 mg/mL echinacoside + 0.1 mg/mL clove oil and 0.09 mg/mL echinacoside + 0.1 mg/mL verapamil were

about 2.58 fold and 1.4 fold higher than of echinacoside alone. And the oral bioavailability of echinacoside (120 mg/kg) in rats administrated with clove oil (0.1 ml/mL) and verapamil (0.2 mg/mL) were significantly improved by 2.36 fold and 1.37 fold, compared with echinacoside alone²⁰⁰.

8.2 Different matrix

The activity and bioavailability of bioactive component can be influenced by the complex chemicals in compound prescriptions. Zhou et al. investigated the pharmacokinetics of forsythoside A in different combinations of SHL, *Scutellariae radix* (SR), *Japonicae flos* (LJF), and *F. fructus* (FF). Compared with FF, C_{max} of forsythoside A in SHL, FF+SR and FF+LJF was increased from 9.830 ng/mL to 30.559, 24.39 and 15.97 ng/mL, respectively. And AUC_{0-1440} of forsythoside A in SHL, FF+SR and FF+LJF were prolonged from 1.210 $\mu\text{g min/mL}$ to 6.879, 3.758, and 3.678 $\mu\text{g min/mL}$, respectively²⁴⁴. In the research of Tanino et al., the dietary of *C. tubulosa* extract enhanced the intestinal absorption of verbascoside and echinacoside to almost three times than pure verbascoside and echinacoside²⁴⁵. Similarly, another study showed that some pharmacokinetic parameters of salidroside after p.o. administration of *Rhodiola crenulata* extract (at a dose containing salidroside 46.2 mg/kg) were not equal to those of pure salidroside. Salidroside in plasma can still be detected after 24 h of oral administration of the *R. crenulata* extract. The $T_{1/2}$ value of salidroside was 7.91 h, which is much larger than that of pure salidroside (1.1 h)¹⁹⁴. The increased bioavailability maybe caused by the following reasons. Firstly, other complex constituents in the matrix of PhGs promoted the absorption of PhGs, and thus increased the bioavailability. Secondly, other compounds were metabolized into compounds with the same m/z as PhGs *in vivo*, and thus the concentration of PhGs was increased. In addition, different dosage could also lead to the observed differences in pharmacokinetic parameters of PhGs.

8.3 β -Cyclodextrin encapsulation

Sheng et al. found the benzene ring of echinacoside can enter into the cavity of β -CD to form echinacoside- β -CD complex, which provided a distinctive method to improve water solubility and thermal stability of echinacoside²⁴⁶. Stability studies made by nuclear magnetic resonance showed that verbascoside enclosed in β -CD complex was more stable than that of free verbascoside²⁴⁷. Verbasoside induced proton shifts and intermolecular ROE signals demonstrated that the caffeoyl moiety of verbascoside is deeply inserted in the cyclodextrin cavity²⁴⁷. It has been reported that the inclusion complex of β -CD and forsythiaside can significantly decrease the degradation –degree of forsythiaside compared with free forsythiaside²⁴⁸. Under

sunshine conditions, almost 90% forsythiaside was degraded after 100 h, while almost 45% of forsythiaside was still remained in forsythiaside inclusion complex²⁴⁸. Forsythiaside A was suffered from a degradation of 11.47% under 75% relative humidity after 10 days. β -CD complex form can significantly improve the stability of forsythiaside A, with the degradation rate of only 4.57% under the same conditions. Under a strong light of 4500 ± 500 Lx, 29.23% of forsythiaside A was degraded, while forsythiaside A was degraded 15.56% in inclusion complex²⁴⁹. Besides, forsythiaside A/ β -CD complex showed higher scavenging free radical ability than forsythiaside A. The IC_{50} of forsythiaside A/ β -CD complex and forsythiaside A were determined as 6.2×10^{-6} and 4.2×10^{-6} M, respectively²⁴⁹.

8.4 Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology is currently one of the hot fields in pharmaceutical research and it has been applied to increase the clinical efficacy of natural products. Nanoparticles have been shown to increase the bioavailability of natural products, by improving the compound's stability within biological systems. Preventing natural products from rapid metabolization in the gastrointestinal tract and liver is also one general mechanism that can increase the bioavailability. In addition, nanoparticles can increase the solubility and transport across membranes of active compounds²⁵⁰.

8.4.1 Liposomes

Isacchi et al. developed and optimized the unilamellar liposomes loaded with verbascoside and tested its advantage in improving the stability and bioavailability of verbascoside. It was demonstrated that liposome was a suitable deliver to enhance the stability and efficiency of verbascoside. Liposomes can prevent the hydrolysis of verbascoside resulting in caffeic acid oxidation. 91% of verbascoside remained in the liposomes after 3 months. In addition, verbascoside liposomes (i. p., 100 mg/kg) showed a prolonged anti-hyperalgesic activity compared with the pure verbascoside in rats at the same dose²⁵¹. Zhao et al. compared the pharmacokinetics and tissue distribution of forsythiaside liposomes (20 mg/kg) and forsythiaside solution (20mg/kg) in chicks by intravenous administration. Compared with forsythiaside solution, the forsythiaside distribution in liver, spleen and lung were obviously increased in forsythiaside liposome. The concentration of forsythiaside in plasm was 14.42 10.72 and 3.70 μ g/mL at 5 min, 10 min and 5min, respectively, for pure forsythiaside, while that for forsythiaside liposome was 35.98, 23.77, and 14.65 μ g/mL, respectively. The forsythiaside liposome could increase the $T_{1/2}$ from 0.11h to 1.79 h, and increase the AUC from 4.26 μ g·h/mL to 39.95 μ g·h/mL, thus prolonged the drug effect time of forsythiaside in the blood circulating system²⁵². Release experiments indicated that the amount of salidroside released from

salidroside liposome was significantly decreased²⁵³. Another experiment showed that salidroside liposome can enhance the plasma concentration and slow down the release rate, thus leading to an increase of its oral bioavailability to 1.77 times in rats²⁵⁴. The activity of promoting skin repair and ameliorating skin inflammation of verbascoside suggests its potential application for cutaneous topical application. It has been reported that verbascoside liposome can not only increase the stability, but also promote verbascoside accumulation into the stratum corneum²⁵⁵ and improve the efficacy of a verbascoside based liposomal eyedrops²⁵⁶. Moreover, salidroside liposome formulation can be used in vaccine delivery systems to realize the controlled release of salidroside²⁵⁷.

8.4.2 Improved liposomes

Peng et al. investigated different delivery systems for controlled release of salidroside and found that the new polymeric liposomes based on amphiphilic chitosan derivatives (DC-Ls) showed better encapsulation potential and slower sustained release rates of salidroside than traditional liposomes (phosphatidylcholine/cholesterol liposomes, PC-Ls)²⁵⁸. The release rate was 82.33% and 66.98% for PC-Ls and DC-Ls after 50 h, respectively. Zhou et al. prepared a series of liposomes such as verbascoside liposome (Ac-Lip), verbascoside/EGCG liposome (AE-Lip), chitosan-coated liposomes (CS-Ac-Lip, CS-AE-Lip) and chitosan-coated liposome tripolyphosphate particles (CS-Ac-Lip-TPP, CS-AE-Lip-TPP). The highest entrapment efficiency was found in CS-Ac-Lip-TPP with the value of 92.74%. CS-AE-Lip-TPP enhanced the bioavailability of verbascoside to 5.32 times, and increased verbascoside contents in different tissues in rats²⁵⁹. After p.o. administration of 200 mg/kg verbascoside to rats, the C_{max} , T_{max} , $T_{1/2}$, and AUC were 0.44 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 0.54 h, 1.83 h and 1.26 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{h/mL}$, respectively. While these values for CS-Ac-Lip (200 mg/kg verbascoside content) were 0.76 mg/mL, 1.92 h, 5.16 h, and 5.58 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{h/mL}$, respectively²⁵⁹. Li et al. prepared a form of cistanche PhGs (CPhGs) liquid proliposomes (CPhGsP). The CPhGsP showed higher encapsulation efficiency and was more stable than CPhGs ordinary liposomes. The plasma levels of echinacoside in rabbits administrated with CPhGsP (25 mg/kg) were higher than those with CPhGs (25 mg/kg) at 5, 15, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, 210, 240 and 360 min. The C_{max} and T_{max} values of proliposomes were 324.23 ng/mL and 30 min, respectively, while that of CPhGs was 193.17 ng/mL and 15 min respectively. Besides that, $AUC_{0-\infty}$ values for CPhGsP group (15494 ng·h/mL) was also higher than CPhGs (24552.14 ng·h/mL). The oral bioavailability of CPhGs was significantly increased by the proliposome formulation, which offers a novel strategy to prepare liposomes for orally administrating of PhGs²⁶⁰.

8.4.3 Other nanoparticles

Cadmium telluride quantum dots (QDs) have attracted the attention of biomedical researchers as they can be used as a novel drug delivery system. Verbasin as a chemotherapeutic agent was successfully fixed into QDs through covalent bonding between the OH group of verbasin and the COOH group of QDs²⁶¹. Treatment of QDs together with verbasin in HepG2/ADM cells caused the apoptosis rate to 90%, much higher than that treatment with verbasin alone (45%). Besides, verbasin QDs effectively inhibited the human HepG2 hepatoma cells growth in mice²⁶¹. Multifunctional verbasin coated Ni nanoparticles²⁶² and Au nanoparticles²⁶³ have also been reported to effectively inhibit the growth and induce the apoptosis of tumor cells *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

To improve the stability and enhance the bioavailability of echinacoside, poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) PLGA encapsulated echinacoside was prepared. The *in vitro* release experiment showed that PLGA-echinacoside released 60% while the pure echinacoside released 90% after four h²⁶⁴. Salidroside-chitosan nanoparticles (SA-CS-NPs) showed sustained release properties with the maximum release rate of 86.55% after 24 h, while pure salidroside reached the maximum release rate in one hour²⁶⁵. Furthermore, pH-sensitive nano-carrier provides another platform to improve the bioavailability of drugs. Peng et al. prepared a new pH-sensitive nano-carrier with poly (acrylic acid) (PAA) as shell-layers and mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) as cores to realize the sustainable release of salidroside. PAA layers had the characteristic of showing closed and opened states in response to different pH values, and thereby regulated the release and uptake of salidroside²⁶⁶.

Salidroside has been demonstrated to possess skin protective effects, but the hydrophilicity of salidroside cause its poor permeability and absorption²⁶⁷. A nanosphere-gel delivery system exhibiting controlled release of paeonol and salidroside was successfully prepared. Compared with treatments of paeonol-loaded nanosphere dispersion and salidroside-loaded hydrogel, the nanosphere-hydrogel formulation with paeonol and salidroside decreased the melanin levels to a larger extent in guinea pig skin induced by ultraviolet B²⁶⁸. Besides that, niosomes were also applied as transdermal nanocarriers in salidroside to enhance its transdermal delivery²⁶⁹. Niosomes have the advantage of less susceptible to oxidation, more stable, and less costly²⁷⁰. The bioavailability of topically administrated drugs can be improved by niosomes through increasing the skin permeability²⁷¹. Zhang et al. prepared niosomes loaded with salidroside and investigated its uptake in two kinds of skin cells. The niosomal formulations delivered more amount of salidroside (2.3 times) across the skin than that in aqueous solution²⁷².

8.5 Other methods

As liposomes exhibit many disadvantages mentioned above, and silica nanoparticles cannot be employed in drug and functional food industries, formulating novel systems for PhGs encapsulation may be an effective way to overcome these problems. Microsphere delivery systems based on natural polymer, such as zein, gelatin, and chitosan microsphere, have attracted widespread attention as they are non-toxic, well biocompatibility, and biodegradability²⁷³⁻²⁷⁵. Luo et al. demonstrated the potential of genipin crosslinked salidroside chitosan in the application of delivering salidroside. They successfully prepared salidroside-chitosan microspheres using genipin which showed less cytotoxicity as a crossing agent. The salidroside stability was improved after being entrapped into chitosan microspheres. The release rate of salidroside from chitosan microspheres was rapid initially, followed by controlled release²⁷⁶. Improved stability and controlled release of salidroside were also achieved through incorporation of salidroside into polymer network microspheres prepared by chitosan and methylcellulose²⁷⁷.

To enhance the intestinal absorption and oral bioavailability, echinacoside-phospholipid complex was prepared. Compared with echinacoside alone, the echinacoside phospholipid complex could significantly increase the absorption rate and P_{eff} to 2.82 fold and 3.39 fold, respectively. Besides, the echinacoside phospholipid complex could increase the C_{max} and AUC_{0-1} to 2.5 and 2.1 times, respectively²⁷⁸.

9. Perspectives

Almost 50 years ~~has been passed~~ have passed since the isolation of the first PhGs, and plenty of experimental data have demonstrated the potent pharmacological activities of PhGs. However, many issues remain unresolved concerning their effective applications in clinic at present. Firstly, of all the over 572 compounds, reported pharmacological studies only focused on limited number of compounds such as salidroside, verbascoside, echinacoside, forsythoside, and isoverbascoside. Other compounds exhibiting excellent pharmacological activities should also be investigated in depth. And also, 1310 articles about PhGs have been published so far, but 612 of them are from China, followed by Japan (144), Turkey (111), USA (55) and Italy (51). It is necessary to attract the attention of pharmacologists from other countries to carry on researches in PhGs. Another important aspect is that the mode of action and the structure activity relationships of PhGs are still not quite clear. Besides, although a large number of laboratory data illuminate the therapeutic effect of PhGs in various diseases, detailed clinical data are still quite limited. It is expected that the therapeutic potential of PhGs will be further explored with more PhGs identified, the further

clarification of the mechanism of action and structure-activity relationships, as well as more clinical trials carried out on the safety and efficiency of PhGs. In addition, many factors such as different processing methods, different food matrix, bio-encapsulation, as well as the addition of lipids can influence the bioavailability of PhGs. Thus, detailed relevant researches are required to identify the optimum conditions to improve the bioavailability of PhGs. What is more, although the present article summarized the different approaches to increase the bioavailability and efficacy of PhGs in different experimental models, studies about improving PhGs bioavailability and efficacy have not been conducted in human. Therefore, further research to enhance the bioavailability of these valuable phytochemicals are needed for human use.

References

1. Cai T, Verze P, Massenio P, et al. Rhodiola rosea, folic acid, zinc and biotin (EndEP®) is able to improve ejaculatory control in patients affected by lifelong premature ejaculation: Results from a phase I-II study. *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine*. 2016;12(4):2083-2087.
2. Jiménez C, Riguera R. Phenylethanoid glycosides in plants: structure and biological activity. *Natural product reports*. 1994;11(6):591-606.
3. Xue Z, Yang B. Phenylethanoid glycosides: Research advances in their phytochemistry, pharmacological activity and pharmacokinetics. *Molecules*. 2016;21(8):991.
4. Xue J, Wang Y, Jia X, Du C, Tang W. Classification and research progress on phenylethanoid glycosides. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018;37(5):282-289.
5. Fu Z, Fan X, Wang X, Gao X. Cistanches Herba: An overview of its chemistry, pharmacology, and pharmacokinetics property. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2018;219:233-247.
6. Dong Z, Lu X, Tong X, Dong Y, Tang L, Liu M. Forsythiae Fructus: A Review on its Phytochemistry, Quality Control, Pharmacology and Pharmacokinetics. *Molecules*. 2017;22(9):1466.
7. Luo H, Wu H, Yu X, et al. A review of the phytochemistry and pharmacological activities of Magnoliae officinalis cortex. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2019.
8. Ma Q, Guo Y, Liu W, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides from Houttuynia cordata and their hepatoprotective activities. *Chemistry of Natural Compounds*. 2016;52(4):761-763.
9. Alipieva K, Korkina L, Orhan I E, Georgiev M I. Verbascoside — A review of its occurrence, (bio)synthesis and pharmacological significance. *Biotechnology Advances*. 2014;32(6):1065-1076.
10. Fu G, Pang H, Wong Y H. Naturally occurring phenylethanoid glycosides: potential leads for new therapeutics. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*. 2008;15(25):2592-2613.
11. Sugiyama M, Kikuchi M. Phenylethanoid glycosides from Osmanthus asiaticus. *Phytochemistry*. 1993, 32(6): 1553-1555.
12. Suzuki N, Miyase T, Ueno A. Phenylethanoid glycosides of Sesamum indicum. *Phytochemistry*. 1993, 34(3): 729.
13. He Z D, Ueda S, Akaji M, et al. Monoterpenoid and phenylethanoid glycosides from Ligustrum pedunculare. *Phytochemistry*. 1994, 36(3): 709-716.
14. Aoshima H, Miyase T, Ueno A. Phenylethanoid glycoside from Veronica undulata. *Phytochemistry*. 1994, 36(6): 1557-1558.
15. Ismail L D, El-Azizi M M, Khalifa T I, et al. Verbascoside derivatives and iridoid glycosides from Penstemon crandallii[J]. *Phytochemistry*, 1995, 39(6): 1391-1393.
16. Miyase T, Yamamoto R, Ueno A. Phenylethanoid glycosides from Stachys officinalis. *Phytochemistry*. 1996, 43(2): 475-479.

17. Zhou B N, Bahler B D, Hofmann G A, et al. Phenylethanoid Glycosides from *Digitalis purpurea* and *Penstemon linarioides* with PKC α -Inhibitory Activity. *Journal of ~~natural-Natural products~~Products*. 1998, 61(11): 1410-1412.
18. Li J X, Li P, Tezuka Y, et al. Three phenylethanoid glycosides and an iridoid glycoside from *Picrorhiza scrophulariiflora*. *Phytochemistry*. 1998, 48(3): 537-542.
19. Kirmizibekmez H, Piacente S, Bassarello C, et al. New phenylethanoid glycosides from *Globularia alypum*. *Planta Medica*. 2007, 73(09): 389.
20. Feng W S, Zang X Y, Zheng X K, et al. A new phenylethanoid glycoside from *Rabdosia lophanthoides* (Buch.-Ham. ex D. Don) Hara. *Chinese Chemical Letters*. 2009, 20(4): 453-455.
21. Martin F, Quinteros V, Hay A E, et al. New phenylethanoid glycosides from *Jacaranda caucana* (Bignoniaceae). *Planta Medica*. 2008, 74(09): 127.
22. Si C L, Deng X J, Liu Z, et al. Studies on the phenylethanoid glycosides with anti-complement activity from *Paulownia tomentosa* var. *tomentosa* wood. *Journal of Asian ~~natural-Natural products~~Products researchResearch*. 2008, 10(11): 1003-1008.
23. Morikawa T, Ninomiya K, Kuramoto H, Kamei I, Yoshikawa M, Muraoka O. Phenylethanoid and phenylpropanoid glycosides with melanogenesis inhibitory activity from the flowers of *Narcissus tazetta* var. *chinensis*. *Journal of ~~natural-Natural medicines~~Medicines*. 2016;70(1):89-101.24. Skhirtladze A, Kemertelidze E, Nebieridze V, Ganzera M. Phenylethanoid Glycosides from the Roots of *Digitalis ciliata* Trautv. *Helvetica Chimica Acta*. 2016;99(3):241-245.
24. Skhirtladze A, Kemertelidze E, Nebieridze V, Ganzera M. Phenylethanoid Glycosides from the Roots of *Digitalis ciliata* Trautv. *Helvetica Chimica Acta*. 2016;99(3):241-245.52. Qu Z Y, Zhang Y W, Zheng S W, et al. A new phenylethanoid glycoside from *Orobancha cernua* Loefling. *Natural Product Research*. 2016;30(8):948-953.
25. Ma Q, Wei R, Zhou B, Sang Z, Liu W, Cao Z. Antiangiogenic phenylpropanoid glycosides from *Gynura cusimbua*. *Natural Product Research*. 2017;1-7.
26. Kirmizibekmez H, Kúsz N, Karaca N, Demirci F. Secondary Metabolites from the Leaves of *Digitalis viridiflora*. *Natural Product Communications*. 2017;12(1):59-61.
27. Kuang H, Tang Z, Wang X, Yang B, Wang Z, Wang Q. Chemical constituents from *Sambucus williamsii* Hance fruits and hepatoprotective effects in mouse hepatocytes. *Natural Product Research*. 2018;32(17):2008-2016.
28. Shao S Y, Feng Z M, Yang Y N, Jiang J S, Zhang P C . Eight new phenylethanoid glycoside derivatives possessing potential hepatoprotective activities from the fruits of *Forsythia suspensa*. *Fitoterapia*. 2017;122:132-137.
29. Sahakitpichan P, Chimnoi N, Wongbundit S, Vorasingha A, Ruchirawat S, Kanchanapoom T. Phenylethanoid glycosides from the leaves of *Magnolia hodgsonii*. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2017;21:269-272.
30. Beladjila K A, Berrehal D, De Tommasi N, et al. New phenylethanoid glycosides from *Cistanche phelypaea* and their activity as inhibitors of monoacylglycerol lipase (MAGL). *Planta Medica*. 2018;84(09/10):710-715.
31. Zhang Y, Wang K, Chen H, et al. Anti-inflammatory lignans and phenylethanoid glycosides from the root of *Isodon ternifolius* (D. Don) Kudô. *Phytochemistry*. 2018;153:36-47.
32. Martins G R, da Fonseca T S, Martínez-Fructuoso L, et al. Antifungal ~~Phenylpropanoid phenylpropanoid Glycosides-glycosides~~ from *Lippia rubella*. *Journal of Natural Products*. 2019.
33. Kutluay V M, Ishiuchi K I, Makino T, Saracoglu I. Cytotoxic phenylethanoid glycosides from *Digitalis davisiana* Heywood: Evaluation of structure activity relationships and chemotaxonomical significance of isolated compounds. *Fitoterapia*. 2019;135:90-98.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

Commented [DLN7]: Tidy up references.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

34. da Rocha C Q, de-Faria F M, Marcourt L, et al. Gastroprotective effects of hydroethanolic root extract of *Arrabidaea brachypoda*: Evidences of cytoprotection and isolation of unusual glycosylated polyphenols[J]. *Phytochemistry*, 2017, 135: 93-105.
35. Mari A, Ciocarlan A, Aiello N, et al. Research survey on iridoid and phenylethanoid glycosides among seven populations of *Euphrasia rostkoviana* Hayne from the Alps. *Phytochemistry*.2017, 137: 72-80.
36. He J, Zhu N L, Kong J, et al. A newly discovered phenylethanoid glycoside from *Stevia rebaudiana* Bertoni affects insulin secretion in rat INS-1 Islet β cells. *Molecules*. 2019, 24(22): 4178.
37. Song X Q, Bao J, Sun J, et al. Butenolides, triterpenoids and phenylethanoid glycosides from *Plantago depressa*. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2019, 30: 21-25.
38. Li H X, Xiao C J, Wang M, et al. Four new phenylethanoid glycosides from *Ternstroemia gymnanthera* and their analgesic activities. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2019, 34: 25-29.
39. Zhu J, Shi Y, Wang H, et al. Two new phenylpropanoid glycosides from *Lagotis brachystachya* Maxim and their Xanthione Oxidase inhibitions. *Natural Product Research*. 2019: 1-6.
40. Hamed A, Pasdaran A, Pasdaran A. A trisaccharide phenylethanoid glycoside from *Scrophularia flava* Grau with potential anti-type 2 diabetic properties by inhibiting α -glucosidase enzyme and decreasing oxidative stress. *Bioorganic Chemistry*. 2020: 103776.
41. Jedrejek D, Pawelec S, Piwowarczyk R, et al. Identification and occurrence of phenylethanoid and iridoid glycosides in six Polish broomrapes (*Orobancha* spp. and *Phelipanche* spp., *Orobanchaceae*). *Phytochemistry*. 2020, 170: 112189.
42. D'Ambrosio M, Ciocarlan A, Aricu A. Minor acetylated metabolites from *Euphrasia rostkoviana*. Natural and synthetic acetylated derivatives of rutin. *Natural product research*. 2020, 34(2): 290-295.
43. Niu C, Li Q, Yang L P, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides from *Callicarpa macrophylla* Vahl. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2020, 38: 65-69.
44. Shu P, Fei Y, Li J, et al. Two new phenylethanoid glycosides from *Ginkgo biloba* leaves and their tyrosinase inhibitory activities. *Carbohydrate Research*. 2020: 108059.
45. Jensen S R. Caffeoyl phenylethanoid glycosides in *Sanango racemosum* and in the Gesneriaceae. *Phytochemistry*.1996, 43(4): 777-783.
46. Qu J B, Xie C F, Ji M, et al. Water - soluble constituents from the liverwort *Marchantia polymorpha*. *Helvetica Chimica Acta*. 2007, 90(11): 2109-2115.
47. Lee Y G, Seo K H, Lee D S, et al. Phenylethanoid glycoside from *Forsythia koreana* (Oleaceae) flowers shows a neuroprotective effect. *Brazilian Journal of Botany*. 2018;41(3):523-528.
48. Liu P, Takaishi Y, Duan H Q. Two new phenylethanoid glycosides from the roots of *Phlomis umbrosa*. *Chinese Chemical Letters*. 2007, 18(2): 155-157.
49. She G M, Wang D, Zeng S F, et al. New Phenylethanoid Glycosides and Sugar Esters from *Ku - Ding - Cha*, a Herbal Tea Produced from *Ligustrum purpurascens*. *Journal of food science*. 2008, 73(6): C476-C481.
50. Ata A, Kalhari K S, Samarasekera R. Chemical constituents of *Barleria prionitis* and their enzyme inhibitory and free radical scavenging activities. *Phytochemistry Letters*.2009, 2(1): 37-40.
51. Zhu J, Shi Y, Wang H, et al. Two new phenylpropanoid glycosides from *Lagotis brachystachya* Maxim and their Xanthione Oxidase inhibitions. *Natural Product Research*. 2019: 1-6.
52. Qu Z Y, Zhang Y W, Zheng S W, et al. A new phenylethanoid glycoside from *Orobancha cernua* Loeffling. *Natural Product Research*. 2016;30(8):948-953.
53. Shao S Y, Zhang F, Feng Z M, Yang Y N, Jiang J S, Zhang P C. Neuroprotective phenylethanoid glycosides with dioxane units from the fruits of *Forsythia suspensa*. *Tetrahedron*. 2017;73(44):6262-6267.
54. Srinroch C, Sahakitpichan P, Techasakul S, et al. Benzyl and phenylethanoid glycosides from the leaves of *Magnolia sirindhorniae*. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2019, 30: 205-209.

Formatted: Font: Italic

55. Kao Y T, Li H Y, Yen I C, et al. New phenylethanoid from the flower of *Osmanthus fragrans* and their bioactivities on human dermal fibroblasts. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2020, 36: 127-133.
56. Shao S Y, Feng Z M, Yang Y N, Jiang J S, Zhang P C. Forsythenethosides A and B: two new phenylethanoid glycosides with a 15-membered ring from *Forsythia suspensa*. *Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry*. 2017;15(33):7034-7039.
57. Hasegawa T, Fukuyama Y, Yamada T, et al. Structures of magnolosides B and C. Novel phenylpropanoid glycosides with allopyranose as core the sugar unit. *Chemical and pharmaceutical bulletin*. 1988, 36(3): 1245-1248.
58. Seidel V, Bailleul F, Libot F, et al. A phenylpropanoid glycoside from *Ballota nigra*. *Phytochemistry*. 1997, 44(4): 691-693.
59. Çalis I, Kirmizibekmez H, Rügger H, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides from *Globularia trichosantha*. *Journal of natural products*. 1999, 62(8): 1165-1168.
60. Sahpaz S, Hennebelle T, Bailleul F. Marruboside, a new phenylethanoid glycoside from *Marrubium vulgare* L. *Natural product letters*. 2002, 16(3): 195-199.
61. Karioti A, Skaltsa H, Heilmann J, et al. Acylated flavonoid and phenylethanoid glycosides from *Marrubium velutinum*. *Phytochemistry*. 2003, 64(2): 655-660.
62. Çalış İ, Kirmizibekmez H. Glycosides from *Phlomis lunariifolia*. *Phytochemistry*. 2004, 65(18): 2619-2625.
63. Sena Filho J G, Nimmo S L, Xavier H S, et al. Phenylethanoid and lignan glycosides from polar extracts of *Lantana*, a genus of verbenaceous plants widely used in traditional herbal therapies. *Journal of natural products*. 2009, 72(7): 1344-1347.
64. Ata A, Kalhari K S, Samarasekera R. Chemical constituents of *Barleria prionitis* and their enzyme inhibitory and free radical scavenging activities. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2009, 2(1): 37-40.
65. De Marino S, Festa C, Zollo F, et al. Antioxidant activity of phenolic and phenylethanoid glycosides from *Teucrium polium* L. *Food Chemistry*. 2012, 133(1): 21-28.
66. Porter E A, Kite G C, Veitch N C, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides in tepals of *Magnolia salicifolia* and their occurrence in flowers of *Magnoliaceae*. *Phytochemistry*. 2015, 117: 185-193.
67. Zhou X L, Wen Q W, Lin X, et al. A new phenylethanoid glycoside with antioxidant and anti-HBV activity from *Tarphochlamys affinis*. *Archives of Pharmacal Research*. 2014;37(5):600-605.
68. Li L, Tsao R, Liu Z, et al. Isolation and purification of acteoside and isoacteoside from *Plantago psyllium* L. by high-speed counter-current chromatography. *Journal of Chromatography A*. 2005;1063(1-2):161-169.
69. Petreska J, Stefova M, Ferreres F, et al. Potential bioactive phenolics of Macedonian *Sideritis* species used for medicinal "Mountain Tea". *Food Chemistry*. 2011;125(1):13-20.
70. Wu Y T, Lin L C, Sung J S, Tsai T H. Determination of acteoside in *Cistanche deserticola* and *Boschniakia rossica* and its pharmacokinetics in freely-moving rats using LC-MS/MS. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2006;844(1):89-95.
71. Zhang W, S X Huo, Y L Wen, et al. Pharmacokinetics of acteoside following single dose intragastric and intravenous administrations in dogs. *Chinese Journal of Natural Medicines*. 2015;13:634-640.
72. Jia C, Shi H, Wu X, Li Y, Chen J, Tu P. Determination of echinacoside in rat serum by reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet detection and its application to pharmacokinetics and bioavailability. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2006;844(2):308-313.
73. Zhang C, Ma W, Zhang Y, et al. Pharmacokinetics, Bioavailability, and Tissue Distribution Study of Angoroside C and Its Metabolite Ferulic Acid in Rat Using UPLC-MS/MS. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2018;9.
74. Wang G N, Pan R L, Liao Y H, Chen Y, Tang J T, Chang Q. An LC-MS/MS method for determination

- of forsythiaside in rat plasma and application to a pharmacokinetic study. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2010;878(1):102-106.
75. Qian H, Lu D, Li W, Zhou X, Wu B, Ma Z. Validated UPLC/Q-TOF-MS Method for Determination of Poliumoside in Rat Plasma and Its Application to Pharmacokinetic Study. *American Journal of Analytical Chemistry*. 2016;7(03):266.
76. Feng B, Song Y, Xu Q, et al. Simultaneous determination of savaside A, acteoside, and isoacteoside in rat plasma by UHPLC-MS/MS: Comparative pharmacokinetic and bioavailability characteristics of *Monochasma savatieri* via different routes of administration. *Journal of Separation Science*. 2018;41(24):4408-4418.
77. Zhang M, Ren X, Yue S, et al. Simultaneous quantification of four phenylethanoid glycosides in rat plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and its application to a pharmacokinetic study of *Acanthus ilicifolius* Herb. *Molecules*. 2019, 24(17): 3117.
78. Guo N, Hu Z, Fan X, et al. Simultaneous determination of salidroside and its aglycone metabolite p-tyrosol in rat plasma by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Molecules*. 2012;17(4):4733-4754.
79. Pan J, Yuan C, Lin C, Jia Z, Zheng R. Pharmacological activities and mechanisms of natural phenylpropanoid glycosides. *Die Pharmazie-An International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2003;58(11):767-775.
80. Radev R. Pharmacological effects of phenylethanoid glycosides. *J Clin Med*. 2010;2:20-3.
81. Liu J, Yang L, Dong Y, Zhang B, Ma X. Echinacoside, an inestimable natural product in treatment of neurological and other disorders. *Molecules*. 2018;23(5):1213.
82. Tao H, Wu X, Cao J, et al. *Rhodiola* species: A comprehensive review of traditional use phytochemistry, pharmacology, toxicity, and clinical study. *Medicinal research reviews*. 2019;39(5):1779-1850.
83. Eldesoky A H, Abdel - Rahman R F, Ahmed O K, et al. Antioxidant and hepatoprotective potential of *Plantago major* growing in Egypt and its major phenylethanoid glycoside, acteoside. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*. 2018, 42(5): e12567.
84. Ahn J H, Jo Y H, Kim S B, et al. Identification of antioxidant constituents of the aerial part of *Plantago asiatica* using LC-MS/MS coupled DPPH assay[J]. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2018, 26:20-24.
85. Jiang Y, Mao S, Huang W, et al. Phenylethanoid glycoside profiles and antioxidant activities of *Osmanthus fragrans* Lour. flowers by UPLC/PDA/MS and simulated digestion model. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*. 2016, 64(12): 2459-2466.
86. Ge L, Zhang W, Zhou G, et al. Nine phenylethanoid glycosides from *Magnolia officinalis* var. *biloba* fruits and their protective effects against free radical-induced oxidative damage. *Scientific Reports*. 2017;7:45342.
87. Li M, Xu T, Zhou F, et al. Neuroprotective Effects of Four Phenylethanoid Glycosides on H₂O₂-Induced Apoptosis on PC12 Cells via the Nrf2/ARE Pathway. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2018;19(4):1135.
88. Yang J, Ju B, Yan Y, et al. Neuroprotective effects of phenylethanoid glycosides in an in vitro model of Alzheimer's disease. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine*. 2017, 13(5): 2423-2428.
89. Yang J, Ju B, Yan Y, et al. Neuroprotective effects of phenylethanoid glycosides in an in vitro model of Alzheimer's disease. *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine*. 2017;13(5):2423-2428.
90. Gong X, Xu Y, Ren K, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides from *Paraboea martinii* protect rat pheochromocytoma (PC12) cells from hydrogen peroxide-induced cell injury. *Bioscience, biotechnology, and biochemistry*. 2019, 83(12): 2202-2212.
91. Ji S, Li S, Zhao X, et al. Protective role of phenylethanoid glycosides, Torenoside B and Savatiside A, in Alzheimer's disease. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine*. 2019, 17(5): 3755-3767.

92. Geng X, Song L, Pu X, Tu P. Neuroprotective effects of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Cistanche salsa* against 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1, 2, 3, 6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP)-induced dopaminergic toxicity in C57 mice. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2004;27(6):797-801.
93. Lu Z, Jiang G, Chen Y, et al. Salidroside attenuates colistin-induced neurotoxicity in RSC96 Schwann cells through PI3K/Akt pathway. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*. 2017;271:67-78.
94. Oertel W H, Ellgring H. Parkinson's disease—medical education and psychosocial aspects. *Patient Education and Counseling*. 1995;26(1-3):71-79.
95. Pu X, Li X, Li H, Tu P, Song Z, Li C. Campneoside II of *Cistanche tubulosa* (Schenk) R. Wight protects neurons from apoptosis induced by neurotoxin 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium (MPP+). *Journal of Peking University (Health Sciences)*. 2001;33:217-220.
96. Sheng G, Pu X, Lei L, Tu P, Li C. Tubuloside B from *Cistanche salsa* rescues the PC12 neuronal cells from 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium ion-induced apoptosis and oxidative stress. *Planta Medica*. 2002;68(11):966-970.
97. Li M, Zhou F, Xu T, Song H, Lu B. Acteoside protects against 6-OHDA-induced dopaminergic neuron damage via Nrf2-ARE signaling pathway. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*. 2018;119:6-13.
98. Jia J, Yan X, Cai Z, et al. The effects of phenylethanoid glycosides, derived from *Herba cistanche*, on cognitive deficits and antioxidant activities in male SAMP8 mice. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part A*. 2017, 80(22): 1180-1186.
99. Chen W, Lin H R, Wei C M, et al. Echinacoside, a phenylethanoid glycoside from *Cistanche deserticola*, extends lifespan of *Caenorhabditis elegans* and protects from A β -induced toxicity. *Biogerontology*. 2018, 19(1): 47-65.
100. Liu Y G, Li X, Xiong D C, Yu B, Pu X, Ye X S. Synthetic phenylethanoid glycoside derivatives as potent neuroprotective agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 2015;95:313-323.
101. Liu S, Han Y, Zhang T, Yang Z. Protective effect of trifluoperazine on hydrogen peroxide-induced apoptosis in PC12 cells. *Brain Research Bulletin*. 2011;84(2):183-188.
102. Ning X, Guo Y, Wang X, et al. Design, synthesis, and biological evaluation of (e)-3, 4-dihydroxystyryl aralkyl sulfones and sulfoxides as novel multifunctional neuroprotective agents. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 2014;57(10):4302-4312.
103. Xiong Q, Hase K, Tezuka Y, Tani T, Namba T, Kadota S. Hepatoprotective activity of phenylethanoids from *Cistanche deserticola*. *Planta Medica*. 1998;64(02):120-125.
104. Shen T, Li X, Hu W, et al. Hepatoprotective effect of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Incarvillea compacta* against CCl₄-induced cytotoxicity in HepG2 cells. *Journal of the Korean Society for Applied Biological Chemistry*. 2015;58(4):617-625.
105. Luo H, Cao R, Wang L, Zhu L. Protective effect of *Cistanche A* on ethanol-induced damage in primary cultured mouse hepatocytes. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2016;83:1071-1079.
106. Li X, Gou C, Yang H, Qiu J, Gu T, Wen T. Echinacoside ameliorates D-galactosamine plus lipopolysaccharide-induced acute liver injury in mice via inhibition of apoptosis and inflammation. *Scandinavian Journal of Gastroenterology*. 2014;49(8):993-1000.
107. Yuan Heng G, Li Li C, Bing Z, et al. Hepatoprotective effect of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Cistanche deserticola* against chronic hepatic injury induced by alcohol. *Food Science*. 2018, 39(13): 176-183.
108. Park S, Son M J, Yook C S, Jin C, Lee Y S, Kim H J. Chemical constituents from aerial parts of *Caryopteris incana* and cytoprotective effects in human HepG2 cells. *Phytochemistry*. 2014;101:83-90.
109. Morikawa T, Pan Y, Ninomiya K, et al. Acylated phenylethanoid oligoglycosides with hepatoprotective activity from the desert plant *Cistanche tubulosa*. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*. 2010;18(5):1882-1890.

110. Ye Y, Song Y, Zhuang J, Wang G, Ni J, Xia W. Anticancer effects of echinacoside in hepatocellular carcinoma mouse model and HepG2 cells. *Journal of Cellular Physiology*. 2019;234(2):1880-1888.
111. Li Z, Lin H, Gu L, Gao J, Tzeng C M. Herba Cistanche (Rou Cong-Rong): One of the best pharmaceutical gifts of traditional Chinese medicine. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2016;7:41.
112. Zhao G, Shi A, Fan Z, Du Y. Salidroside inhibits the growth of human breast cancer in vitro and in vivo. *Oncology Reports*. 2015;33(5):2553-2560.
113. Li H, Huang D, Hang S. Salidroside inhibits the growth, migration and invasion of Wilms' tumor cells through down-regulation of miR-891b. *Life sciences*. 2019;222:60-68.
114. Kang D Y, Sp N, Kim D H, et al. Salidroside inhibits migration, invasion and angiogenesis of MDA-MB 231 TNBC cells by regulating EGFR/Jak2/STAT3 signaling via MMP2. *International Journal of Oncology*. 2018;53(2):877-885.
115. Yu G, Li N, Zhao Y, Wang W, Feng X L. Salidroside induces apoptosis in human ovarian cancer SKOV3 and A2780 cells through the p53 signaling pathway. *Oncology letters*. 2018;15(5):6513-6518.
116. Qi Z, Tang T, Sheng L, et al. Salidroside inhibits the proliferation and migration of gastric cancer cells via suppression of Src-associated signaling pathway activation and heat shock protein 70 expression. *Molecular Medicine Reports*. 2018;18(1):147-156.
117. Kong Y H, Xu S P. Salidroside prevents skin carcinogenesis induced by DMBA/ TPA in a mouse model through suppression of inflammation and promotion of apoptosis. *Oncology Reports*. 2018;39(6):2513-2526.
118. Lv C, Huang Y, Liu Z X, Yu D, Bai Z M. Salidroside reduces renal cell carcinoma proliferation by inhibiting JAK2/STAT3 signaling. *Cancer Biomarkers*. 2016;17(1):41-47.
119. Fan X J, Wang Y, Wang L, Zhu M. Salidroside induces apoptosis and autophagy in human colorectal cancer cells through inhibition of PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway. *Oncology Reports*. 2016;36(6):3559-3567.
120. Li J, Li J, Aipire A, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides from *Cistanche tubulosa* inhibits the growth of B16-F10 cells both in vitro and in vivo by induction of apoptosis via mitochondria-dependent pathway. *Journal of Cancer*. 2016;7(13):1877.
121. Chen X, Tang W J, Shi J B, Liu M M, Liu X H. Therapeutic strategies for targeting telomerase in cancer. *Medicinal research reviews*. 2019.
122. Kirmizibekmez H, Masullo M, Festa M, Capasso A, Piacente S. Steroidal glycosides with antiproliferative activities from *Digitalis trojana*. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2014;28(4):534-538.
123. Encalada M A, Rehecho S, Ansorena D, Astiasarán I, Cavero R Y, Calvo M I. Antiproliferative effect of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Verbena officinalis* L. on colon cancer cell lines. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*. 2015;63(2):1016-1022.
124. Nagao T, Abe F, Okabe H. Antiproliferative constituents in the plants 7. Leaves of *Clerodendron bungei* and leaves and bark of *C. trichotomum*. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2001;24(11):1338-1341.
125. Yogosawa S, Yamada Y, Yasuda S, Sun Q, Takizawa K, Sakai T. Dehydrozingerone, a structural analogue of curcumin, induces cell-cycle arrest at the G2/M phase and accumulates intracellular ROS in HT-29 human colon cancer cells. *Journal of Natural Products*. 2012;75(12):2088-2093.
126. Harput U S, Genc Y, Saracoglu I. Cytotoxic and antioxidative activities of *Plantago lagopus* L. and characterization of its bioactive compounds. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*. 2012;50(5):1554-1559.
127. Mulani S K, Guh J H, Mong K K T. A general synthetic strategy and the anti-proliferation properties on prostate cancer cell lines for natural phenylethanoid glycosides. *Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry*. 2014;12(18):2926-2937.
128. Dembitsky V M. Astonishing diversity of natural surfactants: 5. Biologically active glycosides of aromatic metabolites. *Lipids*. 2005;40(9):869-900.

129. Pan M H, Chiou Y S, Tsai M L, Ho C T. Anti-inflammatory activity of traditional Chinese medicinal herbs. *Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*. 2011;1(1):8-24.
130. Wu A, Yang Z, Huang Y, et al. Natural phenylethanoid glycosides isolated from *Callicarpa kwangtungensis* suppressed lipopolysaccharide-mediated inflammatory response via activating Keap1/Nrf2/HO-1 pathway in RAW 264.7 macrophages cell. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2020: 112857.
131. Li L, Wan G, Han B, Zhang Z. Echinacoside alleviated LPS-induced cell apoptosis and inflammation in rat intestine epithelial cells by inhibiting the mTOR/STAT3 pathway. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2018;104:622-628.
132. Lee J H, Lee J Y, Kang H S, et al. The effect of acteoside on histamine release and arachidonic acid release in RBL-2H3 mast cells. *Archives of Pharmacal Research*. 2006;29(6):508.
133. Song H S, Choi M Y, Ko M S, et al. Competitive inhibition of cytosolic Ca²⁺-dependent phospholipase A 2 by acteoside in RBL-2H3 cells. *Archives of Pharmacal Research*. 2012;35(5):905-910.
134. Yamada P, Iijima R, Han J, Shigemori H, Yokota S, Isoda H. Inhibitory effect of acteoside isolated from *Cistanche tubulosa* on chemical mediator release and inflammatory cytokine production by RBL-2H3 and KU812 cells. *Planta Medica*. 2010;76(14):1512-1518.
135. Jing W, Chunhua M, Shumin W. Effects of acteoside on lipopolysaccharide-induced inflammation in acute lung injury via regulation of NF- κ B pathway in vivo and in vitro. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*. 2015;285(2):128-135.
136. Gao H, Cui Y, Kang N, et al. Isoacteoside, a dihydroxyphenylethyl glycoside, exhibits anti-inflammatory effects through blocking toll-like receptor 4 dimerization. *British journal of pharmacology*. 2017;174(17):2880-2896.
137. Wang Y, Zhao H, Lin C, et al. Forsythiaside A Exhibits Anti-inflammatory Effects in LPS-Stimulated BV2 Microglia Cells Through Activation of Nrf2/HO-1 Signaling Pathway. *Neurochemical Research*. 2016, 41(4):659-665.
138. Pan C W, Zhou G Y, Chen W L, et al. Protective effect of forsythiaside A on lipopolysaccharide/d-galactosamine-induced liver injury. *International Immunopharmacology*. 2015;26(1):80-85.
139. Luan F, Li M, Han K, et al. Phenylethanoid glycosides of *Phlomis younghusbandii* Mukerjee ameliorate acute hypobaric hypoxia-induced brain impairment in rats. *Molecular immunology*. 2019, 108: 81-88.
140. Han M F, Zhang X, Zhang L Q, Li Y M. Iridoid and phenylethanol glycosides from *Scrophularia umbrosa* with inhibitory activity on nitric oxide production. *Phytochemistry Letters*. 2018;28:37-41.
141. Yang B Y, Liu Y, Jiang H B, et al. Phenylpropanoids from the fruits of *Nicandra physaloides* and their anti-inflammatory activities. *Natural Product Research*. 2017;31(22):2634-2640.
142. Liu Y L, He W J, Mo L, et al. Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory activities and toxicology of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Monochasma savatieri* Franch. ex Maxim. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2013;149(2):431-437.
143. Nazemiyeh H, Rahman M M, Gibbons S, et al. Assessment of the antibacterial activity of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Phlomis lanceolata* against multiple-drug-resistant strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Journal of Natural Medicines*. 2008;62(1):91-95.
144. Bazzaz B S F, Khameneh B, Ostad M R Z, Hosseinzadeh H. In vitro evaluation of antibacterial activity of verbascoside, lemon verbena extract and caffeine in combination with gentamicin against drug-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* clinical isolates. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*. 2018;8(3):246.
145. Qu H, Zhang Y, Chai X, Sun W. Isoforsythiaside, an antioxidant and antibacterial phenylethanoid glycoside isolated from *Forsythia suspensa*. *Biorganic Chemistry*. 2012;40:87-91.

146. Qu H, Zhang Y, Wang Y, Li B, Sun W. Antioxidant and antibacterial activity of two compounds (forsythiaside and forsythin) isolated from *Forsythia suspensa*. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2008;60(2):261-266.
147. Kuang H X, Xia Y G, Liang J, Yang B Y, Wang Q H. Lianqiaoxinoside B, a novel caffeoyl phenylethanoid glycoside from *Forsythia suspensa*. *Molecules*. 2011;16(7):5674-5681.
148. Song X, He J, Xu H, et al. The antiviral effects of acteoside and the underlying IFN- γ -inducing action. *Food & Function*. 2016;7(7):3017-3030.
149. Li C, Dai Y, Zhang S X, et al. Quinoid glycosides from *Forsythia suspensa*. *Phytochemistry*. 2014;104:105-113.
150. Li H, Wu J, Zhang Z, et al. Forsythoside A inhibits the avian infectious bronchitis virus in cell culture. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2011;25(3):338-342.
151. Law A H Y, Yang C L H, Lau A S Y, Chan G C F. Antiviral effect of forsythoside A from *Forsythia suspensa* (Thunb.) Vahl fruit against influenza A virus through reduction of viral M1 protein. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2017;209:236-247.
152. Hu X P, Shao M M, Song X, et al. Anti-influenza virus effects of crude phenylethanoid glycosides isolated from *Ligustrum purpurascens* via inducing endogenous interferon- γ . *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2016;179:128-136.
153. Kırmızıbekmez H, Çalis I, Perozzo R, et al. Inhibiting activities of the secondary metabolites of *Phlomis brunneogaleata* against parasitic protozoa and plasmodial enoyl-ACP reductase, a crucial enzyme in fatty acid biosynthesis. *Planta medica*. 2004, 70(08): 711-717.
154. Rocha L G, Almeida J, Macedo R O, et al. A review of natural products with antileishmanial activity. *Phytomedicine*. 2005, 12(6-7): 514-535.
155. Maquiaveli C C, Lucon-Júnior J F, Brogi S, et al. Verbascoside inhibits promastigote growth and arginase activity of *Leishmania amazonensis*. *Journal of natural products*. 2016, 79(5): 1459-1463.
156. Abdelkader H, Alani A W, Alany R G. Recent advances in non-ionic surfactant vesicles (niosomes): self-assembly, fabrication, characterization, drug delivery applications and limitations. *Drug Delivery*. 2014;21(2):87-100.
157. Kyriakopoulou I, Magiatis P, Skaltsounis A L, Aligiannis N, Harvala C. Samioside, a New Phenylethanoid Glycoside with Free-Radical Scavenging and Antimicrobial Activities from *Phlomis*. *Journal of Natural Products*. 2001;64(8):1095-1097.
158. Hamed A, Pasdaran A, Pasdaran A. A trisaccharide phenylethanoid glycoside from *Scrophularia flava* Grau with potential anti-type 2 diabetic properties by inhibiting α -glucosidase enzyme and decreasing oxidative stress. *Bioorganic Chemistry*. 2020: 103776.
159. Morikawa T, Ninomiya K, Imamura M, et al. Acylated phenylethanoid glycosides, echinacoside and acteoside from *Cistanche tubulosa*, improve glucose tolerance in mice. *Journal of Natural Medicines*. 2014;68(3):561-566.
160. Shimada H, Urabe Y, Okamoto Y, et al. Major constituents of *Cistanche tubulosa*, echinacoside and acteoside, inhibit sodium-dependent glucose cotransporter 1-mediated glucose uptake by intestinal epithelial cells. *Journal of Functional Foods*. 2017;39:91-95.
161. Kim J K, Lee Y S, Kim S H, Bae Y S, Lim S S. Inhibition of aldose reductase by phenylethanoid glycoside isolated from the seeds of *Paulownia coreana*. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2011;34(1):160-163.
162. El-Marasy S A, El-Shenawy S M, Moharram F A, et al. Antidiabetic and Antioxidant Effects of Acteoside from *Jacaranda mimosifolia* Family Biognoniaceae in Streptozotocin–Nicotinamide Induced Diabetes in Rats. *Open Access Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2020, 8(A): 125-133.
163. Wu X, He W, Zhang H, Li Y, Liu Z, He Z. Acteoside: A lipase inhibitor from the Chinese tea *Ligustrum*

- purpurascens kudingcha. *Food Chemistry*. 2014;142:306-310.
164. Yang R M, Liu F, He Z D, et al. Anti-obesity effect of total phenylpropanoid glycosides from *Ligustrum robustum* Blume in fatty diet-fed mice via up-regulating leptin. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2015;169:459-465.
165. Li F, Yang Y, Zhu P, et al. Echinacoside promotes bone regeneration by increasing OPG/RANKL ratio in MC3T3-E1 cells. *Fitoterapia*. 2012;83(8):1443-1450.
166. Yang X, Li F, Yang Y, Shen J, Zou R, Zhu P. Efficacy and safety of echinacoside in a rat osteopenia model. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2013.
167. Li F, Yang X, Yang Y, et al. Antiosteoporotic activity of echinacoside in ovariectomized rats. *Phytomedicine*. 2013;20(6):549-557.
168. Xu X, Zhang Z, Wang W, Yao H, Ma X. Therapeutic effect of cistanoside A on bone metabolism of ovariectomized mice. *Molecules*. 2017;22(2):197.
169. Campo G, Pavasini R, Biscaglia S, et al. Platelet aggregation values in patients with cardiovascular risk factors are reduced by verbascoside treatment. A randomized study. *Pharmacological Research*. 2015;97:1-6.
170. Qiu H, Fu P, Fan W, et al. Treatment of primary chronic glomerulonephritis with *Rehmannia glutinosa* acetosides in combination with the angiotensin receptor blocker irbesartan: a randomized controlled trial. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2014;28(1):132-136.
171. Zhang H, Shen W S, Gao C H, Deng L C, Shen D. Protective effects of salidroside on epirubicin-induced early left ventricular regional systolic dysfunction in patients with breast cancer. *Drugs in R&D*. 2012;12(2):101-106.
172. Guo Q, Zhou Y, Wang C J, et al. An open-label, nonplacebo-controlled study on *Cistanche tubulosa* glycoside capsules (Memoregain®) for treating moderate Alzheimer's disease. *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementias®*. 2013;28(4):363-370.
173. An J, Yi T. *Cistanche* total glycosides capsule in the treatment of 99 cases of vascular dementia. *Journal of Shaanxi College of Traditional Chinese Medicine*. 2011;34(02):36-37.
174. Peng Q, Sun C, Ye C, Bai J, Xie S, Huang Y. Effect and the mechanism of *cistanche* total glycosides on cognitive function in patients with thalamic infarction. *Shandong Medical Journal*. 2015;55(25):64-66.
175. Yuan B, Zhao W, Chen J, Sun Y. A randomized controlled double-blind clinical trial of *cistanche* total glycosides capsule in the treatment of neuropsychiatric symptoms of dementia. *Chin J Mod Drug Appl*. 2009;3(18):30-32.
176. Li N, Wang J, Ma J, et al. Neuroprotective Effects of *cistanche* herba therapy on patients with moderate Alzheimer's Disease. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2015, 2015.
177. Zhou W, Tam K Y, Meng M, Shan J, Wang S, Ju W Di L. Pharmacokinetics screening for multi-components absorbed in the rat plasma after oral administration of traditional Chinese medicine *Flos Lonicerae Japonicae*-*Fructus Forsythiae* herb couple by sequential negative and positive ionization ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography/tandem triple quadrupole mass spectrometric detection. *Journal of Chromatography A* 2015;1376:84-97.
178. Shang X, Pan H, Li M, Miao X, Ding H. *Lonicera japonica* Thunb.: ethnopharmacology, phytochemistry and pharmacology of an important traditional Chinese medicine. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2011;138(1):1-21.
179. Li M, Yang H M, Luo D X, Chen J Z, Shi H J. Multi-dimensional analysis on Parkinson's disease questionnaire-39 in Parkinson's patients treated with *Bushen Huoxue* Granule: a multicenter, randomized, double-blinded and placebo controlled trial. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*. 2016;29:116-120.
180. Zhou F, Zhao Y, Li M, et al. Degradation of phenylethanoid glycosides in *Osmanthus fragrans* Lour. flowers and its effect on anti-hypoxia activity. *Scientific reports*. 2017;7(1):10068.

181. Vertuani S, Beghelli E, Scalambra E, et al. Activity and stability studies of verbascoside, a novel antioxidant, in dermo-cosmetic and pharmaceutical topical formulations. *Molecules*. 2011;16(8):7068-7080.
182. Oyourou J N, Combrinck S, Regnier T, Marston A. Purification, stability and antifungal activity of verbascoside from *Lippia javanica* and *Lantana camara* leaf extracts. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 2013;43:820-826.
183. Wong I Y F, He Z D, Huang Y, Chen Z Y. Antioxidative activities of phenylethanoid glycosides from *Ligustrum purpurascens*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2001;49(6):3113-3119.
184. Arthur H, Joubert E, De Beer D, Malherbe C J, Witthuhn R C. Phenylethanoid glycosides as major antioxidants in *Lippia multiflora* herbal infusion and their stability during steam pasteurisation of plant material. *Food Chemistry*. 2011;127(2):581-588.
185. D'Imperio M, Cardinali A, D'Antuono I, et al. Stability–activity of verbascoside, a known antioxidant compound, at different pH conditions. *Food Research International*. 2014;66:373-378.
186. Cardinali A, Linsalata V, Lattanzio V, Ferruzzi M G. Verbascosides from Olive Mill Waste Water: Assessment of Their Bioaccessibility and Intestinal Uptake Using an in Vitro Digestion/Caco-2 Model System. *Journal of Food Science*. 2011;76(2), H48-H54.
187. Yan Y, Liu T X, Bi D, et al. Transformation pathways in methanol of echinacoside, a principal effective ingredient of *Cistanches Herba*. *China journal of Chinese materia medica*. 2018, 43(11): 2321-2325.
188. Karioti A, Fani E, Vincieri F F, Bilia A R. Analysis and stability of the constituents of *Curcuma longa* and *Harpagophytum procumbens* tinctures by HPLC-DAD and HPLC–ESI-MS. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. 2011;55(3):479-486.
189. Wen Y, Huo S, Zhang W, et al. Pharmacokinetics, biodistribution, excretion and plasma protein binding studies of acteoside in rats. *Drug Research*. 2016;66(03):148-153.
190. Sun X, Liao Q, Liu G, et al. Simultaneous determination of three phenylethanoid glycosides from *Callicarpae Caulis et Folium* in rat plasma by LC–MS/MS and its application to PK study. *Bioanalysis*. 2013;5(15):1883-1895.
191. Yang H, Wang G, Hao H, et al. A sensitive and specific liquid chromatography/ tandem mass spectrometry method for determination of echinacoside and its pharmacokinetic application in rats. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 2009;23(6):630-637.
192. Chang Y W, Yao H T, Hsieh S H, Lu T J, Yeh T K. Quantitative determination of salidroside in rat plasma by on-line solid-phase extraction integrated with high-performance liquid chromatography/electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2007;857(1):164-169.
193. Yu S, Liu L, Wen T, et al. Development and validation of a liquid chromatographic/ electrospray ionization mass spectrometric method for the determination of salidroside in rat plasma: Application to the pharmacokinetics study. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2008;861(1):10-15.
194. Zhang J, Chen X, Wang P, et al. LC–MS Determination and Pharmacokinetic Study of Salidroside in Rat Plasma after Oral Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicinal Preparation *Rhodiola crenulata* Extract. *Chromatographia*. 2008;67(9-10):695-700.
195. Gao Y, Zong C, Liu F, et al. Evaluation of the intestinal transport of a phenylethanoid glycoside-rich extract from *Cistanche deserticola* across the Caco-2 cell monolayer model. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(2):e0116490.
196. Zhou F, Huang W, Li M, Zhong Y, Wang M, Lu B. Bioaccessibility and Absorption Mechanism of Phenylethanoid Glycosides Using Simulated Digestion/Caco-2 Intestinal Cell Models. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2018;66(18):4630-4637.
197. Cardinali A, Rotondo F, Minervini F, et al. Assessment of verbascoside absorption in human colonic

- tissues using the Ussing chamber model. *Food Research International*. 2013;54(1):132-138.
198. Li Y, Gan L, Li G Q, Deng L, Zhang X, Deng Y. Pharmacokinetics of plantamajoside and acteoside from *Plantago asiatica* in rats by liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. 2014;89:251-256.
199. Matthias A, Blanchfield J T, Penman K G, et al. Permeability studies of alkylamides and caffeic acid conjugates from echinacea using a Caco - 2 cell monolayer model. *Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics*. 2004;29(1):7-13.
200. Shen J Y, Yang X L, Yang Z L, Kou J P, Li F. Enhancement of absorption and bioavailability of echinacoside by verapamil or clove oil. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy*. 2015;9:4685.
201. Matthias A, Addison R S, Penman K G, Dickinson R G, Bone K M, Lehmann R P. Echinacea alkamide disposition and pharmacokinetics in humans after tablet ingestion. *Life Sciences*. 2005;77(16):2018-2029.
202. Zhou W, Di L, Bi X, Chen L, Du Q. Intestinal absorption of forsythoside A by rat circulation in situ. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica*. 2010;45(45):1373-1378.
203. Zhou W, Di L Q, Wang J, et al. Intestinal absorption of forsythoside A in in situ single-pass intestinal perfusion and in vitro Caco-2 cell models. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*. 2012;33(8):1069.
204. Li Y, Peng C, Ye L H, Zhang R Q, Jiang X H. Investigation on the absorption of phillyrin and forsythiaside in rat digestive tract. *European Journal of Drug Metabolism and Pharmacokinetics*. 2011;36(2):79-85.
205. Cui Q, Pan Y, Bai X, Zhang W, Chen L, Liu X. Systematic characterization of the metabolites of echinacoside and acteoside from *Cistanche tubulosa* in rat plasma, bile, urine and feces based on UPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MS. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 2016;30:1406-1415.
206. Zhang Y F, Liu L J, Xu F, Shang M Y, Liu G X, Cai S Q. Investigation of the in Vivo Metabolism of Sibirioside A and Angoroside C in Rats by HPLC-ESI-IT-TOF-MSn. *Molecules*. 2018;23(10):2702.
207. Zhang Y, Li L, Lin L, Liu J, Zhang Z, Xu D, Xiang F. Pharmacokinetics, tissue distribution, and excretion of salidroside in rats. *Planta Medica*. 2013;79(15):1429-1433.
208. Guo N, Zhu M, Han X, Sui D, Wang Y, Yang Q. The metabolism of salidroside to its aglycone p-tyrosol in rats following the administration of salidroside. *PLoS One*. 2014;9(8), e103648.
209. Qi M, Xiong A, Li P, Yang Q, Yang L, Wang Z. Identification of acteoside and its major metabolites in rat urine by ultra-performance liquid chromatography combined with electrospray ionization quadrupole time-of-flight tandem mass spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2013;940:77-85.
210. Su D, Li W, Xu Q, Liu Y, Song Y, Feng Y. New metabolites of acteoside identified by ultra-performance liquid chromatography/quadrupole-time-of-flight MSE in rat plasma, urine, and feces. *Fitoterapia*. 2016;112:45-55.
211. Jia C, Shi H, Jin W, et al. Metabolism of echinacoside, a good antioxidant, in rats: isolation and identification of its biliary metabolites. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*. 2009;37(2):431-438.
212. Wang Y, Hao H, Wang G, et al. An approach to identifying sequential metabolites of a typical phenylethanoid glycoside, echinacoside, based on liquid chromatography–ion trap-time of flight mass spectrometry analysis. *Talanta*. 2009;80(2):572-580.
213. Song Q, Li J, Huo H, et al. Retention Time and Optimal Collision Energy Advance Structural Annotation Relied on LC–MS/MS: An Application in Metabolite Identification of an Antidementia Agent Namely Echinacoside. *Analytical Chemistry*. 2019, 91(23): 15040-15048.
214. Wang F, Cao G S, Li Y, et al. Characterization of forsythoside A metabolites in rats by a combination of UHPLC-LTQ-Orbitrap mass spectrometer with multiple data processing techniques. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 2018;32(5), e4164.
215. Deng R, Xu Y, Feng F, Liu W. Identification of poliumoside metabolites in rat feces by high performance liquid chromatography coupled with quadrupole time-of-flight tandem mass

- spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2014;969:285-296.
216. Qian H, Yu F J, Lu D Y Wu, et al. Identification of poliumoside metabolites in rat plasma, urine, bile, and intestinal bacteria with UPLC/Q-TOF-MS. *Chinese Journal of Natural Medicines*. 2018;16(11):871-880.
217. Luo Z, Ma X, Liu Y, et al. An approach to characterizing the complicated sequential metabolism of salidroside in rats. *Molecules*. 2016;21(6):706.
218. Li Y, Peng Y, Ma P, et al. In vitro and in vivo metabolism of Cistanche tubulosa extract in normal and chronic unpredictable stress-induced depressive rats. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2019, 1125: 121728.
219. Sousa T, Paterson R, Moore V, Carlsson A, Abrahamsson B, Basit A W. The gastrointestinal microbiota as a site for the biotransformation of drugs. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2008;363(1-2):1-25.
220. Cui Q, Pan Y, Xu X, et al. The metabolic profile of acteoside produced by human or rat intestinal bacteria or intestinal enzyme in vitro employed UPLC-Q-TOF-MS. *Fitoterapia*. 2016;109:67-74.
221. Lei L, Song Z H, Tu P F, Li Y Z, Wu L J, Chen F K. Metabolic regulation of phenylethanoid glycosides from Herba cistanches in dogs' gastrointestinal. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica*. 2001;36(6): 432-435.
222. Zhang W X, Yang B, Hu Y M, et al. Effect of rat intestinal flora in vitro on metabolites of acteoside. *China journal of Chinese Materia Medica*. 2016;41(8):1541-1545.
223. Li Y, Zhou G, Xing S, Tu P, Li X. Identification of echinacoside metabolites produced by human intestinal bacteria using ultraperformance liquid chromatography–quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2015;63(30):6764-6771.
224. Xing S, Peng Y, Wang M, Chen D, Li X. In vitro human fecal microbial metabolism of Forsythoside A and biological activities of its metabolites. *Fitoterapia*. 2014;99:159-165.
225. Li Y, Zhou G, Peng Y, Tu P, Li X. Screening and identification of three typical phenylethanoid glycosides metabolites from Cistanches Herba by human intestinal bacteria using UPLC/Q-TOF-MS. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. 2016;118:167-176.
226. Li Y, Peng Y, Wang M, Tu P, Li X. Human gastrointestinal metabolism of the Cistanches Herba water extract in vitro: elucidation of the metabolic profile based on comprehensive metabolite identification in gastric juice, intestinal juice, human intestinal bacteria, and intestinal microsomes. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2017;65(34):7447-7456.
227. Peyrol J, Riva C, Amiot M J. Hydroxytyrosol in the prevention of the metabolic syndrome and related disorders. *Nutrients*. 2017, 9(3): 306.
228. Wu S, Zhang Y, Ren F, et al. Structure–affinity relationship of the interaction between phenolic acids and their derivatives and β -lactoglobulin and effect on antioxidant activity. *Food chemistry*. 2018, 245: 613-619.
229. Wang X, Chang X, Luo X, et al. An integrated approach to characterize intestinal metabolites of four phenylethanoid glycosides and intestinal microbes-mediated antioxidant activity evaluations in vitro using UHPLC-Q-Exactive high resolution mass spectrometry and a 1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl-based assay. *Frontiers in pharmacology*. 2019, 10: 826.
230. Liu Y H, Lu Y L, Han C H, et al. Inhibitory activities of acteoside, isoacteoside, and its structural constituents against protein glycation in vitro. *Botanical studies*. 2013, 54(1): 6.
231. Cui Q, Pan Y, Zhang W, et al. Metabolites of dietary acteoside: profiles, isolation, identification, and hepatoprotective capacities. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*. 2018, 66(11): 2660-2668.
232. Lee K, Lee B J, Bu Y. Protective effects of dihydrocaffeic acid, a coffee component metabolite, on a focal cerebral ischemia rat model. *Molecules*. 2015, 20(7): 11930-11940.
233. Kim K H, Kim S, Jung M Y, et al. Anti-inflammatory phenylpropanoid glycosides from Clerodendron trichotomum leaves. *Archives of pharmacal research*. 2009, 32(1): 7-13.
234. Gómez-Ruiz J Á, Leake D S, Ames J M. In vitro antioxidant activity of coffee compounds and their

- metabolites. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*. 2007, 55(17): 6962-6969.
235. Cook T J, Shenoy S S. Intestinal permeability of chlorpyrifos using the single-pass intestinal perfusion method in the rat. *Toxicology*. 2003, 184(2-3): 125-133.
236. Mazzaferro S, Bouchemal K, Skanji R, et al. Intestinal permeation enhancement of docetaxel encapsulated into methyl- β -cyclodextrin/poly (isobutylcyanoacrylate) nanoparticles coated with thiolated chitosan. *Journal of controlled release*. 2012, 162(3): 568-574.
237. Surampalli G, K. Nanjwade B, Patil P A. Corroboration of naringin effects on the intestinal absorption and pharmacokinetic behavior of candesartan cilexetil solid dispersions using in-situ rat models. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 2015, 41(7): 1057-1065.
238. Ahmed I S, Hassan M A, Kondo T. Effect of lyophilized grapefruit juice on P-glycoprotein-mediated drug transport in-vitro and in-vivo. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 2015, 41(3): 375-381.
239. Sen R, Natarajan K, Bhullar J, et al. The novel BCR-ABL and FLT3 inhibitor ponatinib is a potent inhibitor of the MDR-associated ATP-binding cassette transporter ABCG2. *Molecular cancer therapeutics*. 2012, 11(9): 2033-2044.
240. Xiang Q, Zhang D, Wang J, et al. Cabozantinib reverses multidrug resistance of human hepatoma HepG2/adr cells by modulating the function of P - glycoprotein. *Liver International*. 2015, 35(3): 1010-1023.
241. Zhou F. The bioavailability mechanism analysis and the improvement based on nano-delivery system of Phenylethanoid glycosides. [D]. Zhejiang University, 2018.
242. Zhou W, Qin K M, Shan J J, et al. Improvement of intestinal absorption of forsythoside A in weeping forsythia extract by various absorption enhancers based on tight junctions. *Phytomedicine*. 2012;20(1):47-58.
243. Zhou W, Tan X, Shan J, Liu T, Cai B, Di L. Effect of chito-oligosaccharide on the intestinal absorptions of phenylethanoid glycosides in Fructus Forsythiae extract. *Phytomedicine*. 2014;21(12):1549-1558.
244. Zhou W, Di L Q, Shan J J, Bi X L, Chen L T, Wang L C. Intestinal absorption of forsythoside A in different compositions of Shuang-Huang-Lian. *Fitoterapia*. 2011;82(3):375-382.
245. Tanino T, Nagai N, Funakami Y. Phloridzin - sensitive transport of echinacoside and acteoside and altered intestinal absorption route after application of Cistanche tubulosa extract. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2015;67(10):1457-1465.
246. Sheng Z, Tian Y, Hu X, Jin Z, Xu X, Cheng A. Identification and releasing characteristics of β -cyclodextrin-phenylethanoid glycosides inclusion complex. *Journal of Inclusion Phenomena and Macrocyclic Chemistry*. 2014;79(3-4):437-442.
247. Isacchi B, Karioti A, Bergonzi C, Bilia A. Characterization of salvianolic acid B and verbascoside cyclodextrin complexes by innovative NMR methods. Evaluation of their stability. *Planta Medica*. 2010;76(12):534.
248. Hou X, Zhou X, Li Q, Lu Y, Sun Y, Wu G. Preparation of forsythiaside-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex and its characters. *Animal Husbandry and Feed Science*. 2014;6(2):46-65.
249. Jia J, Huo L, Zhang L. Study on inclusion behaviour of forsythiaside A with β -cyclodextrin. *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids*. 2018;56(4):438-451.
250. Nile S H , Baskar V , Selvaraj D , et al. Nanotechnologies in Food Science: Applications, Recent Trends, and Future Perspectives. *Nano-Micro Letters*. 2020, 12(1):1-34.
251. Isacchi B, Bergonzi M C, Iacopi R, Ghelardini C, Galeotti N, Bilia A R. Liposomal formulation to increase stability and prolong antineuropathic activity of verbascoside. *Planta Medica*. 2017;83(05):412-419.
252. Zhao H J, Xu W K, Jia Z H, et al. Study on Pharmacokinetics of Forsythiaside Liposome in

- Chicks. *China Animal Husbandry & Veterinary Medicine*. 2014;41(2):153-158.
253. Fan M, Xu S, Xia S, Zhang X. Effect of different preparation methods on physicochemical properties of salidroside liposomes. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2007;55(8):3089-3095.
254. Mao Z F, Liu L Y, Liu J M, Yu S H, Gu G M. Pharmacokinetics of Salidroside Liposomes in Rats. *Chinese Journal of Experimental Traditional Medical Formulae*. 2011;3:202-204.
255. Sinico C, Caddeo C, Valenti D, Fadda A M, Bilia A R, Vincieri F F. Liposomes as carriers for verbascoside: stability and skin permeation studies. *Journal of Liposome Research*. 2008;18(1):83-90.
256. Ambrosone L, Guerra G, Cinelli M, et al. Corneal epithelial wound healing promoted by verbascoside-based liposomal eyedrops. *BioMed Research International*. 2014;1-8.
257. Feng Y, Zhao X, Lv F, et al. Optimization on preparation conditions of salidroside liposome and its immunological activity on PCV-2 in mice. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2015.
258. Peng H, Li W, Ning F, et al. Amphiphilic chitosan derivatives-based liposomes: synthesis, development, and properties as a carrier for sustained release of salidroside. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2014;62(3):626-633.
259. Zhou F, Xu T, Zhao Y, et al. Chitosan-coated liposomes as delivery systems for improving the stability and oral bioavailability of acteoside. *Food Hydrocolloids*. 2018;83:17-24.
260. Li M, Li Y, Liu W, et al. The preparation of Cistanche phenylethanoid glycosides liquid proliposomes: Optimized formulation, characterization and proliposome dripping pills in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2016;93:224-232.
261. Zhao X H, Yue H L, Li P, Zeng X, Zhang G. Evaluation of the antitumor activity by CdTe QDs with verbascoside. *Nano*. 2013;8(03):1350031.
262. Chen M, Zhang Y, Huang B, et al. Evaluation of the antitumor activity by Ni nanoparticles with verbascoside. *Journal of Nanomaterials*. 2013;26.
263. Zhang Y, Liu B, Wu H, et al. Anti-tumor activity of verbascoside loaded gold nanoparticles. *Journal of Biomedical Nanotechnology*. 2014;10(12):3638-3646.
264. Su S S, Chen W, Fang H, Li J, Zhang Y, Han B. Formula optimization of echinacoside-loaded PLGA nanoparticles by Box-Behnken design and response surface method. *Chinese Journal of New Drugs*. 2016;25(9):1069-1074.
265. He L, Deng L, Deng Y. Preparation and in vitro drug release properties of salidroside-chitosan nanoparticles. *Chinese Traditional and Herbal Drugs*. 2013;44: 552-556.
266. Peng H, Dong R, Wang S, et al. A pH-responsive nano-carrier with mesoporous silica nanoparticles cores and poly (acrylic acid) shell-layers: fabrication, characterization and properties for controlled release of salidroside. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2013;446(1-2):153-159.
267. Chiang H M, Chien Y C, Wu C H, et al. Hydroalcoholic extract of *Rhodiola rosea* L.(Crassulaceae) and its hydrolysate inhibit melanogenesis in B16F0 cells by regulating the CREB/MITF/tyrosinase pathway. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 2014;65:129-139.
268. Peng L H, Xu S Y, Shan Y H, et al. Sequential release of salidroside and paeonol from a nanosphere-hydrogel system inhibits ultraviolet B-induced melanogenesis in guinea pig skin. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*. 2014;9:1897.
269. Abdel-Mageed W M, Backheet E Y, Khalifa A A, Ibraheim Z Z, Ross S A. Antiparasitic antioxidant phenylpropanoids and iridoid glycosides from *Tecoma mollis*. *Fitoterapia*. 2012;83(3):500-507.
270. Marianecchi C, Di Marzio L, Rinaldi F, et al. Niosomes from 80s to present: the state of the art. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*. 2014;205:187-206.
271. Zidan A S, Habib M J. Maximized mucoadhesion and skin permeation of anti-AIDS-loaded niosomal gels. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2014;103(3):952-964.

272. Zhang Y, Zhang K, Wu Z, et al. Evaluation of transdermal salidroside delivery using niosomes via in vitro cellular uptake. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2015;478(1):138-146.
273. Kawadkar J, Chauhan M K. Intra-articular delivery of genipin cross-linked chitosan microspheres of flurbiprofen: preparation, characterization, in vitro and in vivo studies. *European journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*. 2012;81(3):563-572.
274. Lan Y, Li W, Guo R, Zhang Y, Xue W, Zhang Y. Preparation and characterisation of vancomycin-impregnated gelatin microspheres/silk fibroin scaffold. *Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition*. 2014;25(1):75-87.
275. Tran T H, Ramasamy T, Poudel B K, et al. Preparation and characterization of spray-dried gelatin microspheres encapsulating ganciclovir. *Macromolecular Research*. 2014;22(2):124-130.
276. Luo M, Peng H, Deng Z, Yin Z, Zhao Q, Xiong H. Preparation and characterization of genipin-crosslinked chitosan microspheres for the sustained release of salidroside. *International Journal of Food Engineering*. 2015;11(3):323-333.
277. Chen Z, Ning F, He X, Peng H, Xiong H. Controlled Release of Salidroside Microspheres Prepared Using a Chitosan and Methylcellulose Interpenetrating Polymer Network. *International Journal of Food Engineering*. 2017;13(10).
278. Li F, Yang X, Yang Y, Li P, Yang Z, Zhang C. Phospholipid complex as an approach for bioavailability enhancement of echinacoside. *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*. 2015;41(11):1777-1784.

Author's biosketches

Lipeng Wu obtained his bachelor degree from Henan University of Science and Technology (2011), and master degree from Northwest Agricultural and Forestry University (2014). After that, he worked in Institute of Quality Standard and Testing Technology for Agro-Products, Xinjiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences. He became a PhD candidate in Zhejiang University in September 2018. Ever since, the neuro-protective activity of phenylethanoid glycosides has been Mr. Wu's main research focus.

Milen I. Georgiev holds a PhD in biotechnology from the Stephan Angeloff Institute of Microbiology (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences). He has the research focus of phenylethanoid glycosides for 10+ years. He serves as the associate editor of *Phytomedicine* and *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, and the editorial boards of *Biotechnology Letters* and *Chinese Medicine*. He was the Chairman of International Conference on Natural Products Utilization: ~~International Conference on Natural Products Utilization~~, From Plants to Pharmacy Shelf. He has 175 years of experience in natural products field and has published in excess of 1520 papers. He has delivered 50+ invited lectures in 20 different countries. His current research focuses on the biosynthesis of fine molecules and the development of biotechnological tools for their sustainable mass production along with the application of emerging platforms for comprehensive metabolite profiling and biochemometrics. Milen holds several grants from the NSF of Bulgaria and framework programmes of European Union (incl. H2020 – PlantaSYST project, well-funded with €30+5M). At present, he coordinates the project SusMAPWaste @ USAMV in Bucharest (Romania).

Hui Cao received her Ph.D. in Analytical Chemistry at Central South University, China in 2015. During her Ph.D. period, she spent two years to study at the University of Würzburg, Germany. Following two years as a postdoc at the University of Macau. She has extensive experience in the nutritional and phytochemical composition. She is the author of about 50 papers in international scientific journals. She serves as the Managing Editor for eFood and in the editorial advisory board of Anti-cancer Agents in Medicinal Chemistry.

Lutfun Nahar joined the Faculty of Science, LJMU, as an Honorary Lecturer in May 2013. She is the founding member of the Centre for Natural Products Discovery within the School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences. Prior to this current position, she worked as a Senior Lecturer in Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry, and coordinated the Drug Discovery and Design Research Division within the Pharmacy Research Group. She was also the ERASMUS coordinator at UoW (2008-2011). Dr Nahar graduated with a Chemistry (Hons) degree from the University of Exeter and obtained my PhD in Synthetic Organic Medicinal Chemistry from the University of Aberdeen. To date, she has published over 400 peer-reviewed scientific papers, reviews, abstracts, books and book chapters in the area of Synthetic Organic Medicinal and Natural Products Chemistry. Total Google Scholar citations over 10000, h- index: 46. Her research interests include: application of organic synthetic methodologies in different areas of chemistry; Design and synthesis of novel anticancer, antimalarial, antibacterial and antioxidant agents; Design and synthesis of 'nanoparticles' and 'molecular umbrellas' for drug delivery and other application; Synthesis of biologically active macrocyclic polyamines, steroid monomers and dimers; Synthesis of bioactive natural products and pharmaceutically important small molecules; Isolation and structure determination of bioactive phytochemicals and structure activity relationships (SAR) of bioactive compounds.

Hesham R. El-Seedi is working in the area of isolation, structure elucidation and synthesis of biologically active natural products from medicinal plants, marine and bee products. Prof. Hesham is a former fellow of the Japanese Society of Promotion of Science (JSPS), Faculty of Science and Technology, Keio University, Japan, under direction of Prof. Shosuke Yamamura and Prof. S. Nishiyama. Throughout his carrier, he worked in pioneer internationally recognized laboratories including Geneva University, Switzerland, in collaboration with Prof. Kurt Hostettmann, Kunglia Tekniska Högskola (KTH), Stockholm, Sweden (since 2007), Faculty of Pharmacy, Uppsala Biomedical Center, Uppsala University, Sweden and Menoufia University, Egypt. He was appointed as Adjunct Faculty Professor at the International Center for Chemical and Biological Sciences (ICCBS), Karachi, Pakistan, 2017 and was rewarded two Swedish Research Links grants for the 2017-2019. He has published peer-reviewed international research articles

and scientific papers, reviews, chapters in Peer-Reviewed International Journals. He has presented his research at several scientific conferences worldwide. For many years of Scientific Contributions to Pharmacognosy Research and thereby he has increased the knowledge about bioactive Natural Products and built contributions with Developing Countries, Nordic International Conference, Visby, Sweden.

Satyajit D. Sarker obtained his BPharm (Hons) and MPharm (postgraduate) degrees from the University of Dhaka, and secured first class first position in order of merit in both programmes. He completed his PhD in Pharmaceutical Sciences from the University of Strathclyde, under the supervision of one of the pioneers in phytochemistry research in the UK, Professor Peter G Waterman, and also Professor Alexander I Gray. He is a Professor of Pharmacy, and has been the Director of the School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences at the Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU) since 2013. Prior to the current post, he had worked as a Professor of Pharmacy, Deputy Head of Pharmacy and Pharmacy Research Group Leader at the University of Wolverhampton during 2008-2013. He is a well-trained, highly experienced, outstandingly productive, and highly cited internationally known accomplished pharmaceutical, medicinal and natural products chemist, with more than three decades of postgraduate research experience, and 580 publications to his credit. Total Google Scholar citations was over 15,000, and h-index was 56. Prof Sarker served as the Editor-in-Chief of the Wiley journal, *Phytochemical Analysis* in 2010. He is currently in the editorial board of >30 international journals. His research is broadly in the area of pharmaceutical and natural products chemistry as well as in the area of rational drug design (medicinal chemistry). His research focuses on anticancer, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (against multiple-drug-resistant bacterial strains, e.g. MRSA) of purified compounds from higher plants as well as novel synthetic organic compounds.

Jianbo Xiao earned his PhD in nutritional science from Okayama Prefectural University, Japan (2009). He worked as Humboldtian at University of Wuerzburg, Germany (2013-2015), prior to join University of Macau in 2015. Prof. Xiao is currently the Editor-in-Chief of a newly launched *e-Food journal* and *Food Frontiers* (Wiley), the associate editor of *Phytochemical Analysis* (Wiley) and *Journal of Berry Research* (IOS), and in the editorial boards of several international journals, including *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, *Food Chemistry*, *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, *Phytochemistry*, *Industrial Crops and Products*, *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, *Molecules*, *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, *Current Drug Metabolism*, *Anti-Cancer Agents in Medical Chemistry*, and so on. He was the chairman of 2015 International Symposium on Phytochemicals in Medicine and Food (1 - ISPMF2015) organized by PSE and its second edition (2 - ISPMF 2017), third edition (3 - ISPMF 2018). Prof. Xiao

have published and accepted 171 scientific articles on peer-reviewed journals, and 101 of them were as corresponding author and first author. And 28 papers have been selected as ESI highly cited papers. The total cited times of these papers are 5528 with h index=40 (Google, 02/27/2019), and 3859 with h index=34 (Web of Science, 02/27/2019). In addition, he has been selected as 2016, 2017 and 2019 Clarivate Analytics Highly Cited Researcher (HCR).

Baiyi Lu is a professor of Food Science and Nutrition, Zhejiang University, China. Dr. Lu received his PhD in food science in 2007 from Zhejiang University. Afterwards, he joined the faculty as an assistant professor (2007), associate professor (2010), and professor (2018). He worked in department of food science, Cornell University during 2012.1 to 2013.1 as a visiting scholar. He served as the co-editor in chief of *Food Frontiers* and guest editor of *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* and *Food Chemistry*. His research interests have mainly focused on natural products chemistry, biological activity of nutrients, food chemistry and human health. He has published 62 international scientific articles as the first or corresponding author with the average IF₅>5.

Table 1. 101 of the 111 PhGs that have not been summarized before

No.	Compounds	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	Source	Bioactivity	Ref
1	Osmanthuside H	H	OH	H	H	H	H	Api			
2	Osmanthuside I	H	OH	H	H	H	H	A1	<i>Osmanthus asiaticus</i>	ND ^a	11
3	Osmanthuside J	H	OH	H	H	H	H	A2			
4	ND ^a	OH	OH	OH	H	Rha	H	Feru			
5	Lipedosides A-I	OH	OH	H	H	Rha	Cou	H	<i>Ligustrum pedunculare</i>	ND ^a	13
6	Lipedosides A-II	OH	OH	H	H	Rha	H	Cou			
7	ND ^a	OH	OCH ₃	H	Ara	Glc	H	Van	<i>Veronica undulata</i>	ND ^a	14
8	2-O-acetyl-3 ^m -O-methylverbascoside	OH	OH	H	Ace	Rha	Van	H	<i>Penstemon crandallii</i>	ND ^a	15
9	2,4 ^m -di-O-acetyl-3 ^m -O-methylverbascoside	OH	OH	H	Ace	B	Van	H			
10	Betonyosides A	OH	OH	OH	H	Rha	Fer	H			
11	Betonyosides D	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Rha	<i>cis</i> - Fer	Api	<i>Stachys officinalis</i>	ND ^a	16
12	Betonyosides E	OH	OH	H	H	Rha	Fer	Api			
13	Betonyosides F	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Rha	<i>cis</i> - F	H			
14	2-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl)-ethyl-O-(α -l-rhamnosyl)-(1 \rightarrow 3)-O-(α -l-rhamnosyl)-(1 \rightarrow 6)-4-O-E-feruloyl- β -d-glucopyranoside	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Rha	Fer	Glc	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i> and <i>Penstemon linarioides</i>	PKC α -Inhibitory	17
15	Scrosides B	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Glc	H	Fer	<i>Picrorhiza scrophulariiflora</i>	ND ^a	18
16	Scrosides C	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Glc	Fer	H			

17	ND ^a	H	H	H	H	Rha	Caff	Cou	<i>Globularia alypum</i>	ND ^a	19
18	Lophanthoside A	OH	OCH ₃	H	Ace	Rha	H	H	<i>Rabdosia lophanthoides</i>	ND ^a	20
19	ND ^a	OH	OH	H	H	Rha	Caf	D1	<i>Jacaranda caucana</i>	ND ^a	21
20	ND ^a	OH	OH	H	H	Rha	Caf	D2			
21	Isoilicifolioside A	OH	OH	OCH ₂ CH ₃	H	Rha	H	Caf	<i>Paulownia tomentosa</i>	Anticomplement	22
22	Tazettosides D	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	Glc	<i>Narcissus tazetta</i>	Inhibiting melanogenesis	23
23	Digicilisides A	OCH ₃	OH	H	H	Glc	Fer	Rha	<i>Digitalis ciliata</i>	ND ^a	24
24	Digicilisides B	OH	OH	H	Ara	Glc	Fer	Rha			
25	Digicilisides C	OH	OH	H	H	Glc	Caf	E1			
26	α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \leftrightarrow 2)- β -D-[4''-(8E)-7-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-8-propenoate,1''-O-(7S)-7-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-7-methoxyethyl]- glucopyranoside	OH	OH	OCH ₃	Rha	H	Caf	H	<i>Gynura cusimbua</i>	Antiangiogenic	25
27	Digiviridifloroside	OH	OH	H	H	H	Caf	E2	<i>Digitalis viridiflora</i>	Antibacterial	26
28	2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)ethanol-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-O- β -D-glucopyranoside	H	OH	H	Glu	H	H	H	<i>Sambucus williamsii</i>	Hepatoprotective	27
29	Forsythoside M	H	OH	H	H	H	H	Van	<i>Forsythia suspensa</i>	Hepatoprotective	28
30	Forsythoside N	H	OH	H	H	H	H	D4			
31	Forsythoside P	H	OH	H	H	H	Caf	Rha			

32	Hodgsonialloside A	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	H			
33	Hodgsonialloside B	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	H	Glc	H	<i>Magnolia hodgsonii</i>	ND ^a	29
34	Hodgsonialloside C	OCH ₃	OH	H	H	H	H	H			
35	1-β-p-hydroxyphenyl-ethyl-2-O-acetyl-3,6-di-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-β-D-glucopyranoside	H	OH	H	Ace	Rha	H	Rha			
36	1-β-p-hydroxyphenyl-ethyl-3,6-O-di-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-β-D-glucopyranoside	H	OH	H	H	Rha	H	Rha	<i>Cistanche phelypaea</i>	Inhibiting Monoacylglycerol Lipase	30
37	1-β-p-hydroxyphenyl-ethyl-2-O-acetyl-3,6-di-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-4-p-coumaroyl-β-D-glucopyranoside	H	OH	H	Ace	Rha	Cou	Rha			
38	1-β-p-hydroxyphenyl-ethyl-3,6-di-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-4-p-coumaroyl-β-D-glucopyranoside	H	OH	H	H	Rha	Cou	Rha			
39	Ternifolioside F	OH	OCH ₃	H	Ace	G1	Fer	H			
40	Ternifolioside G	OH	OCH ₃	H	Ace	G1	H	Fer	<i>Isodon ternifolius</i>	Antiinflammatory	31
41	Ternifolioside H	OH	OCH ₃	H	Ace	Rha	H	Fer			
42	Lippiarubelloside A	OH	OH	H	H	G2	Caf	H	<i>Lippia rubella</i>	Antifungal	32
43	Lippiarubelloside B	OH	OH	H	H	G3	Cou	H			
44	Digidavoside A	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Glc	Caf	Glc			
45	Digidavoside B	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Glc	Fer	Glc	<i>Digitalis davisiana</i>	Cytotoxic	33
46	Davoside	OH	OH	H	H	Glc	Fer	Rha			

47	3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)ethyl 2-O-[5-O-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybenzoyl)-β-D-apiofuranosyl]-β-D-glucopyranoside	OH	OH	H	A3	H	H	H			
48	3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)ethyl 2-O-[5-O-(3,4-dihydroxybenzoyl)-β-D-apiofuranosyl]-β-D-glucopyranoside	OH	OH	H	A4	H	H	H	<i>Arrabidaea brachypoda</i>	Gastroprotective	34
49	2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-ethyl 1-O-[4-O-feruloyl-2-O-a-L-rhamnopyranosyl-3-O-a-L-rhamnopyranosyl]-β-D-glucopyranoside	OH	OH	H	Rha	Rha	Fer	H			
50	2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-ethyl 1-O-[4-O-coumaroyl-2-O-a-L-rhamnopyranosyl-3-O-a-L-rhamnopyranosyl]-β-D-glucopyranoside	OH	OH	H	Rha	Rha	Cou	H	<i>Euphrasia rostkoviana</i>	ND ^a	35
51	Steviophethanoside	H	OH	H	H	H	H	Ara	<i>Stevia rebaudiana</i>	Antidiabetic	36
52	ND ^a	H	H	H	H	Glc	Caf	H	<i>Plantago depressa</i>	Antiradical	37
53	Terngymnosides A	OH	OH	H	D3	H	H	D4			
54	Terngymnosides B	OH	OH	H	D5	H	H	D4	<i>Ternstroemia gymnanthera</i>	Analgesic	38
55	Terngymnosides C	OH	OH	H	H	H	H	D4			
56	Terngymnosides D	OH	OH	H	F1	H	H	D3			
57	Nepetifosides D	OH	OH	OCH ₃	H	Rha	Fer	Api	<i>Schnabelia nepetifolia</i>	Osteoblast proliferation	39
58	Nepetifosides F	OH	OH	O(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₃	H	Rha	Caf	Api			

59	Flavaioside	OCH ₃	OH	H	H	E3	Fer	Rha	<i>Scrophularia flava</i>	Antidiabetic	40
60	Ramoside A	OH	OH	H	H	Rha	Cou	Rha	<i>Orobanche</i>	Antioxidant	41
61	2'-acetylramoside A	OH	OH	H	Ace	Rha	Cou	Rha	<i>caryophyllacea</i>		
62	Rostkovianoside	OH	OH	H	Rha	Rha	H	H	<i>Euphrasia rostkoviana</i>	ND ^a	42
63	6'-O-acetylcrassifolioside	OH	OH	H	Rha	Rha	Caf	Ace			
64	Macrophyllside E	H	H	H	H	Rha	H	Caf		ND ^a	43
65	Macrophyllside F	OH	OH	OH	OH	Rha	H	Caf			
66	Ginkgoside C	OH	OH	H	Glc	H	H	H	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Tyrosinase inhibitory	44
67	Ginkgoside D	OH	OH	H	H	Glc	H	H			
68	Sanangoside	OH	OH	H	H	Caf	H	H	<i>Sanango racemosum</i>	ND ^a	45
69	2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)ethyl O- A-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)- β-D-allopyranoside	OH	OH	H	Rha	H	H	H			
70	2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)ethyl O- β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→6)-β- D-allopyranoside	OH	OH	H	H	H	H	Xyl	<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	ND ^a	46
71	8'-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)ethyl-O- α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1-4)-2-O- (E)-caffeoyl-α-L-arabinopyranoside	OH	OH	H	cis-Caf	H	Rha	Rha	<i>Forsythia koreana</i>	Neuroprotective	47
72	2'',3''-diacetyl-O-betonyoside D	OH	OCH ₃	Fer	H	Rha	Ace	H			
73	3'',4''-diacetyl-O-betonyoside D	OH	OCH ₃	Fer	H	H	Ace	Ace	<i>Phlomis umbrosa</i>	ND ^a	48

74	Ligupurpurosides C	H	OH	H	Cou	H	H	Rha	<i>Ligustrum purpurascens</i>	Antioxidant	49																																																																																																																																													
75	Ligupurpurosides D	H	OH	H	Caf	H	H	Rha				76	Barlerinoside	OH	OH	Caf	Glc	H	Rha	H	<i>Barleria prionitis</i>	Antioxidant	50	77	Nepetifosides B	OH	OCH ₃	Caf	Api	H	H	H	<i>Schnabelia nepetifolia</i>	Osteoblast proliferation	39	78	nepetifosides C	OH	OCH ₃	Caf	Api	H	H	Xyl	79	Nepetifosides E	OH	OH	Caf	Api	H	H	Xyl	80	Nepetifosides G	H	H	Caf	Api	H	H	H	81	Nepetifosides H	OH	OCH ₃	Cou	Api	H	H	H	82	Nepetifosides K	OH	OH	H	Caf	H	H	Xyl	83	Nepetifosides L	OH	OH	Caf	Rha	H	H	Xyl	84	Lagotiside C	OH	OH	H	Caf	H	H	Glc	<i>Lagotis brachystachya</i>	Inhibiting Xanthione Oxidase	51	85	Scrosides A	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Fer	Glc	H	<i>Picrorhiza scrophulariiflora</i>	ND ^a	18	86	Tazettosides A	F1	H	H					<i>Narcissus tazetta</i>	Inhibiting melanogenesis	23	87	Tazettosides B	F2	H	H					88	Tazettosides C	F2	H	Glc					89	2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)ethanol-3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→6)-O-β-D-glucopyranoside	F3	H	Glc				
76	Barlerinoside	OH	OH	Caf	Glc	H	Rha	H	<i>Barleria prionitis</i>	Antioxidant	50																																																																																																																																													
77	Nepetifosides B	OH	OCH ₃	Caf	Api	H	H	H	<i>Schnabelia nepetifolia</i>	Osteoblast proliferation	39																																																																																																																																													
78	nepetifosides C	OH	OCH ₃	Caf	Api	H	H	Xyl																																																																																																																																																
79	Nepetifosides E	OH	OH	Caf	Api	H	H	Xyl																																																																																																																																																
80	Nepetifosides G	H	H	Caf	Api	H	H	H																																																																																																																																																
81	Nepetifosides H	OH	OCH ₃	Cou	Api	H	H	H																																																																																																																																																
82	Nepetifosides K	OH	OH	H	Caf	H	H	Xyl																																																																																																																																																
83	Nepetifosides L	OH	OH	Caf	Rha	H	H	Xyl																																																																																																																																																
84	Lagotiside C	OH	OH	H	Caf	H	H	Glc	<i>Lagotis brachystachya</i>	Inhibiting Xanthione Oxidase	51																																																																																																																																													
85	Scrosides A	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	Fer	Glc	H	<i>Picrorhiza scrophulariiflora</i>	ND ^a	18																																																																																																																																													
86	Tazettosides A	F1	H	H					<i>Narcissus tazetta</i>	Inhibiting melanogenesis	23																																																																																																																																													
87	Tazettosides B	F2	H	H																																																																																																																																																				
88	Tazettosides C	F2	H	Glc																																																																																																																																																				
89	2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)ethanol-3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→6)-O-β-D-glucopyranoside	F3	H	Glc					<i>Sambucus williamsii</i>	Hepatoprotective	27																																																																																																																																													

90	Forsythoside O	F4	H	Fer			
91	Forsythenside M	F5	H	D6			
92	Forsythenside N	F5	H	Van	<i>Forsythia suspensa</i>	Hepatoprotective	28
93	Rengyoside D	F6	H	Van			
94	Rengyoside E	F6	H	Cou			
95	3'-O-methyl isocrenatoside	Rha	H	Fer	<i>Orobancha cernua</i>	Cytotoxic	52
96	Forsyoxasides A	H	Caf	Rha			
97	Forsyoxasides B	H	<i>cis</i> -Caf	Rha			
98	Forsyoxasides C	H	Cou	Rha	<i>Forsythia suspensa</i>	Neuroprotective	53
99	Forsyoxasides D	H	Caf	Xyl			
100	Forsyoxasides E	Caf	H	Xyl			
101	Forsyoxasides F	H	Caf	H			

Abbreviations: ND^a: Not determined, Glc=β-D-glucopyranose, Ara=α-L-arabinopyranose, Rha=α-L-rhamnopyranose, Xyl=β-D-xylopyranose, Api=β-D-apiofuranose, Cou=Coumaroyl, Caf=Caffeoyl, *cis*-Caf=*cis*-Caffeoyl, Ace=Acetyl, Van=Vanilloyl, Fer=Feruloyl, and *cis*-Fer=*cis*-Feruloyl.

Table 2. Ten of the 111 PhGs that have not been summarized before

No.	Compounds	Source	Bioactivity	Ref
102	Betonyosides B	<i>Stachys officinalis</i>	ND ^a	16
103	Betonyosides C			
104	Nepetifosides I	<i>Schnabelia nepetifolia</i>	Osteoblast proliferation	39
105	Nepetifosides J			
106	(7R)-campneoside I	<i>Magnolia sirindhorniae</i>	ND ^a	54
107	(7S)-campneoside I			
108	Nepetifosides A	<i>Schnabelia nepetifolia</i>	Osteoblast proliferation	39
109	Glucooleoacteoside	<i>Osmanthus fragrans</i>	Inhibit human dermal fibroblasts	55
110	Forsythenethosides A	<i>Forsythia suspensa</i>	Neuroprotective	56
111	Forsythenethosides B			

Compound 102 and 103, and compound 104 and 105 are two pairs of isomers.

Compound 106 and 107 are a pair of diastereomers.

Table 3 Pharmacokinetic parameters of several PhGs

Compound	Dose mg/kg	Model	C_{max} ng/mL	T_{max} min	$T_{1/2}$ h	$AUC_{0 \rightarrow t}$ ng×h/mL	$AUC_{0 \rightarrow \infty}$ ng×h/mL	$MRT_{0 \rightarrow t}$ h	F %	References
Verbascoside	100 p.o.	Rats	130±30	ND	1.54±0.5	ND	ND	ND	0.12	70
	20 p.o.		162±52.6	10.2±4.8	1.49±0.28	165±21.2	181.13±20.55	1.41±0.13	1.11	
Verbascoside	40 p.o.	Rats	312.5±44.4	17.4±10.2	1.05±0.23	364.7±76.1	378.92±75.56	1.36±0.07	1.23	189
	80 p.o.		624.2±187.2	13.2±9	1.45±0.43	577.6±156.9	625.67±179.03	1.32±0.10	0.98	
	10 p.o.		420±100	ND	1.48±0.16	788±145.7	802.83±147.83	1.93±0.15	4.12	
Verbascoside	20 p.o.	Dogs	720±140	ND	1.55±0.36	1464.3±131.3	1491.7±219.17	1.86±0.21	3.84	71
	40 p.o.		1440±240	ND	1.44±0.49	3052.3±478.2	3146.1±498.83	2.05±0.49	4.00	
Verbascoside	26 p.o.		33.2±25.8	16.7±0.23	6.08±1.25	101.29±43.85	150.38±45.14	3.34±0.76		
Forsythoside B	200 p.o.	Rats	224.6±99.2	16.4±0.28	5.00±1.21	0.19±0.08	1020.1±526.1	3.08±0.88	ND	190
Poliumoside	360 p.o.		653.5±311.9	15.8±0.24	3.41±0.81	1211.3±926.2	1518.65±914.9	3.05±0.15		
Verbascoside			1476.7±15.3	30	1.89±0.42	3.711×10 ⁶	3710.9±173.81	2.51±0.21		
Isoacteoside	1000 p.o.	Rats	296±7	20	3.67±0.58	0.767×10 ⁶	766.73±54.77	4.89±0.771	ND	76
Savaside A			288.3±56.1	60	1.33±0.74	0.323×10 ⁶	322.63±135.12	1.65±0.808		
Echinacoside	100 p.o.	Rats	612.2±320.4	15	1.24	1011.75	ND	ND	0.83	72
Echinacoside	10 p.o.	Rats	779.2±211.7	60.0±30.0	1.1±0.3	1931.0±412.5	1982.0±420	2.1±0.4	ND	191
Salidroside	25 p.o.	Rats	6493±1768	66±4.2	ND	ND	8486±2441	1.1±0.2	98	192
Salidroside	12 p.o.	Rats	4300±1100	ND	ND	3376.7±1286	3416.6±1316.6	0.7±0.3	ND	193
Salidroside	46.2 p.o.	Rats	3386±2138	33.6±12.6	7.91±4.42	16146±6558	18599±6529	ND	ND	194
Salidroside	100 i.g.	Rats	3716.7±860	18±6	1.32±0.22	7552.9±549	7724.5±446.6	2.07±0.51	51.9	78
Forsythiaside	100 p.o.	Rats	122.2±45.4	20.0±0.0	1.25±0.22	9508.3±1156	9513.3±1153.3	ND	0.5	73
Poliumoside	200 p.o.	Rats	561.5±100.3	29.7±13.9	0.85±0.19	2433.3±164.7	5422.2±1162.2	0.74±0.29	0.69	74
Angoroside C	100 p.o.	Rats	473.5±77.6	7.5±0.00	1.26±0.18	812.0±216.1	842.4±230.6	1.61±0.27	2.1	75

Abbreviations: ND, not detected; C_{\max} , maximum concentration; T_{\max} , time maximum concentration; $T_{1/2}$, elimination half-life; AUC_{0-t} , area under the concentration-time curve calculated from zero up to the last measured concentration; $AUC_{0-\infty}$, area under the concentration-time curve extrapolated from zero up to infinity; MRT, mean residence time; F, bioavailability; p.o., oral administration, i.g., intragastric gavage.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Distribution of the 572 phenylethanoid glycosides in the plant kingdom.

Figure 2. The representative chemical structure of monosaccharidic PhGs, disaccharidic PhGs, trisaccharidic PhGs, tetrasaccharidic PhGs, and pentasaccharidic PhGs (sugar moiety in red, hydroxyphenylethyl moiety in blue and hydroxycinnamic acid moiety in green).

Figure 3. A: Number of papers indexed in Web of Science related to “Phenylethanoid Glycosides” B: Times Cited of papers related to “Phenylethanoid Glycosides” by papers indexed in Web of Science. C: The number of papers published on specific phenylethanoid glycosides compound. D: The number of papers cited on specific phenylethanoid glycosides compound.

Figure 4. A summary of the potential health benefits of phenylethanoid glycosides.

Figure 5. Various phenylethanoid glycosides based products and medicines.

Figure 6. Main metabolic pathways of PhGs *in vivo* (1: hydrolysis, 2: hydroxylation, 3: sulfation, 4: glucuronidation, 5: acetylation, 6: methylation, 7: hydration, 8: deglycosylation, 9: hydrogenation, 10: dehydroxylation).

Figure 7. Different strategies to improve the bioavailability of phenylethanoid glycosides.